

2-DoF Translational and Rotational Mechanical System for Robotic Catheterization

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Forwarding

We do hereby forward the Thesis entitled “**2-DoF Translational and Rotational Mechanical System for Robotic Catheterization**” submitted by **Dhruva Rajesh Khanzode** (Roll No.:325518002, Registration No.: 325518002 of 2018-2019) under our supervision in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of Master of Technology in Mechatronics from Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur.

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Student Declaration

I hereby declare that the work presented in this Thesis entitled “**2-DoF Translational and Rotational Mechanical System for Robotic Catheterization**”, submitted towards completion of partial fulfilment of the requirement of the Degree of Master of Technology in Mechatronics at Indian Institute of Engineering Science and Technology, Shibpur is an authentic record of my work carried out under the guidance of Dr Ranjan Jha and Dr Subhasis Bhaumik. The project was done in partial compliance with the requirements and constraints of the prescribed curriculum.

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Abstract

Cardiac catheterization is a minimally invasive medical procedure that cardiologists use to diagnose and treat several cardiovascular diseases. The procedure involves the insertion of a catheter inside the body and threaded by the arterial system to the heart. The progress of the catheter is observed by an X-ray imaging device called a fluoroscope. The problems which are being faced by the medical personnel include the high level of x-ray radiation generated by the fluoroscope and that is why several researchers have been drawn into this area of research to develop a teleoperated robotic cardiac catheterization system so that replace the physician in the radiation exposed environment and can be controlled from a radiation-free zone. As several robotic catheterization systems have been developed, but most of them are focused on ablation and angioplasty, and no mechanism is available to manipulate the soft and deformable catheter. The Thesis comprises the study of documented accounts of research published on the effects of fluoroscopic radiation, complications during cardiac catheterization, design, and development of robotic systems for catheterization and their clinical trials. The thesis includes the evolution of the design of the principle drive mechanism for a 2-DoF robotic catheterization system. The robotic catheterization system assembly comprises of 2 independent drive mechanism to allow linear motion as well as rotational motion. The system is designed such that it comprises replaceable parts to maintain sterility. The thesis also includes designing a virtual 3D model of the catheter in CAD software and performing static structural analysis using the Finite Element Method to observe the parameters such as Maximum deformation, Von-Mises stress, and Elastic strain experienced by the catheter of different materials under certain loading conditions. The thesis encompasses the determination of relationships of dynamic force components of the spring specification with physical parameters and it also covers the benefits as well as shortcomings of the robotic catheterization system.

Keywords: Catheterization, Robotics, FEM, Teleoperation, 2 DoF Mechanism, Heart surgery

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Engineering Notations

Symbol	Implication	Unit
F_p	Maximum permissible force	Newton (N)
FoS	Factor of safety	-
F_a	Total applied force	Newton (N)
F_{sf}	Force applied by springs in front assembly	Newton (N)
F_{sr}	Force applied by springs in rear assembly	Newton (N)
F_{kf}	Force applied by one spring in front assembly	Newton (N)
F_{kr}	Force applied by one spring in rear assembly	Newton (N)
m_f	Mass of slider (front)	Kilogram (Kg)
m_r	Mass of slider (rear)	Kilogram (Kg)
μ_s	Coefficient of friction for slider	-
μ_c	Coefficient of friction for catheter	-
d_r	Diameter of rollers	Meter (m)
d_c	Diameter of catheter	Meter (m)
τ_f	Torque provided by the motor (front)	Newton meter (Nm)
τ_r	Torque provided by the motor (rear)	Newton meter (Nm)
g	Acceleration due to gravity	Meter per second square (m/s ²)

Abbreviations and Acronyms

CVDs	:	Cardiovascular Diseases
DoF	:	Degrees of freedom
EP	:	Electrophysiology
FEM	:	Finite Element Method
FFR	:	Fractional flow reserve
ICRP	:	International Commission on Radiological Protection
IVUS	:	Intravascular Ultrasound
PCI	:	Percutaneous Coronary Intervention
PTCA	:	Percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty
PTFE	:	Polytetrafluoroethylene
SMA	:	Shape Memory Alloy
TLD	:	Thermoluminescent dosimeter
VIS	:	Vascular Interventional Surgery

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In today's world filled with stress and a sedentary lifestyle, cardiovascular diseases (CVD) have become the number one cause of death globally, taking an estimated around 18 million lives each year. CVDs are a group of disorders of the heart and blood vessels which include coronary heart diseases, cerebrovascular diseases, rheumatic heart diseases, and other conditions. Cardiac catheterization is a medical procedure used for the diagnosis and treatment of certain cardiovascular conditions. During the cardiac catheterization, a long, thin tube-like structure called a catheter is inserted into the human body. The insertion can be from a femoral approach i.e. Into the femoral artery from the region near the groin, it can be from the radial approach in which the catheter is inserted into the radial artery through the wrist. The catheter is then threaded through the blood vessel up to the heart.

This procedure can be used diagnostically for Cardiac Ventriculography, which involves the injection of dye into the chambers of the heart to measure the volume of blood pumped, or it can be used for Hemodynamic monitoring, which measures the pressure, flow and oxygen saturation of the blood inside the heart. A coronary angiogram is also one of the diagnostic procedures facilitated by cardiac catheterization. This procedure involves inserting the catheter into the coronary blood vessels instead of the heart chambers to detect any possible blockages in the coronary artery restricting the blood flow to the heart. Some diagnostic procedures require a special type of catheters to be used and fractional flow reserve (FFR) and intravascular ultrasound (IVUS) are the prime examples. The FFR needs a catheter with an electronic sensor attached to its tip for measuring the pressure in coronary arteries for detecting and confirming the presence of blockages. IVUS as the name suggests requires a miniature ultrasound probe attached to its tip, which helps in imaging the interior of the coronary artery.

After the diagnosis, cardiac catheterization is also used to treat some heart conditions. Cardiac ablation is a treatment used to cure abnormal heart rhythm or arrhythmia. This procedure requires a special electrophysiological catheter, which scars or destroy arrhythmia causing tissue using radiofrequency energy. Valvuloplasty also called balloon Valvuloplasty is a procedure to open or repair the narrowed opening.

A balloon catheter is used to perform this procedure. Angioplasty is another procedure that uses a catheter for treating the blockages in coronary arteries. Vessel widening and stent placement are done to improve the blood flow from the blocked vessel.

All these procedures are performed under a medical imaging device called a fluoroscope. The fluoroscope produces real-time x-ray images that help in guiding the catheter inside the human body. The radiation from the x-ray emission poses a threat to the physician who performs multiple procedures in a day. The physician requires to wear heavy lead to protect himself from the radiation. As the lead shielding was not deemed enough for radiation protection, the invention of the robotic cardiac catheterization system took place.

Fig.1.1: Cardiac catheters

Fig.1.2: Fluoroscopic image of a catheter inside human heart

1.2 Motivation

Cardiac catheterization is one of the front running techniques in the diagnosis and treatment of heart-related diseases. Now the open-heart surgeries or the bypass surgeries are performed only if the case of the patient is very critical or complicated. Most of the time, cardiac catheterization is preferred over open-heart surgical operations as it has less possibility of occurrence of any complications. With developing technology and the negative effect of the fluoroscope X-ray radiation, as well as the shortcomings of manual cardiac catheterization, has led the researchers across the globe to design a teleoperated robot-assisted cardiac catheterization systems which will assist the physicians to avoid the exposure to the harmful X-ray radiation. Hence, along the lines of that, this thesis was prompted by the following causes. Firstly, the primary aim of this thesis is to eliminate the lengthy exposure to X-ray irradiation of the attending medical staff office and reduce the fatigue of attending medical personnel in performing the surgical process by negating the need for lead garments.

This means the work will sustainably address the challenges. Secondly, all the research being performed in the area of robotic catheterization is generally concentrated on performing cardiac ablation using the electrophysiological (EP) catheter or performing percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI) also called angioplasty robotically.

As far as these procedures fail, the robotically manipulating element is either the EP catheter or the guidewire, which are inflexible and do not receive a chance of deformation. On the other hand, procedures like Ventriculography or hemodynamic monitoring is still done manually and don't convert to robot-assisted because of the flexibility and deformability of the common diagnostic catheter. So to design and acquire such a scheme that can be utilized to move the common flexible diagnostic catheter is a strong motivation for research. Thirdly, and most importantly, sparing the commercially available devices, most devices of cardiac catheterization are not sterile competent, i.e. they are not designed such that sterility can be maintained while performing the medical process. As sterility being one of the most important aspects of a medical procedure, to design such a system which can be medically competent with the sterility standards is also a ground for performing research in this field.

1.3 Robot-assisted Cardiac Catheterization

The robotic cardiac catheterization system is used to operate the movement of the catheter remotely from a radiation insulated chamber. The robotic system can provide linear as well as a rotational motion to the catheter. These robotic systems are designed such that they are able to replicate the movements of the catheter as provided during performing the procedure manually. The accuracy, precision, and sensitivity in motion are very high in these robotic devices. These robotic devices are generally controlled via a controller or joystick for operating the catheter remotely. And due to the electronically controlled motion of the catheter, the travel required by the catheter or the displacement achieved can be calculated.

Some of these devices like Niobe (Stereotaxis Inc., USA) or Amigo (Catheter Precision Inc., USA) are specially designed to be used with cardiac ablation catheters. Commercial devices like Sensei X and Magellan (Hansen Medical Inc., USA) are used for peripheral vascular interventions and CorPath 200 and CorPath GRX (Corindus Vascular Robotics, USA) are designed to be used for percutaneous coronary interventions.

In recent years, clinical studies have shown that the use of robot-assisted catheterization has severely brought down the overall dosage of radiation absorbed by the physician performing the procedure. In these studies, it was also found that the mortality rate as well as the rate of procedural complications have also been reduced whenever the robotic catheterization system was used. Moreover, the procedural time of a robotic catheterization procedure was found to be approximately 5-8 times faster than the conventional standard manual catheterization procedure time.

1.4 Thesis outline

The following thesis has been organized into six chapters. The first chapter introduces the concept of cardiac catheterization, it includes a brief description of the diseases which are the reasons to perform cardiac catheterization, various types of cardiac catheterization procedures, various components involved, and the sequence of operation for the procedure. It also includes the difficulties faced by the operating physician and the harmful effects of radiation exposure. This chapter also briefly introduces the concept of robotic-assisted cardiac catheterization procedures as to how does it work and what devices are the front runners in the international commercial market.

The second chapter consists of the literature survey done in order to gather knowledge about various aspects associated with catheterization and robotic catheterization. This chapter includes some accounts of studies and documented research done on various topics such as the effects of radiation on operating physician during cardiac catheterization, complications arising during and post-cardiac catheterization procedures, designing and development of novel and innovative robotic catheterization systems and accounts of clinical trials to assess the feasibility of such robotic cardiac catheterization devices.

The third chapter incorporates the problem formulation and provides the hypotheses required to carry out research work for the thesis. The fourth chapter primarily deals with the designing and analysis required for developing a robotic catheterization system. The chapter consists of four subparts. The first part deals with the design and development of the catheter driving mechanism for the robotic system.

The second subpart encompasses a virtual recreation of the catheter model in order to perform a finite element analysis to analyze the limiting criteria in terms of applied force and the results in terms of deformation, stress, and elastic strain for catheters made up of different polymeric materials.

The fifth chapter summarizes the results of all the experiments and procedure performed to develop a feasible robotic cardiac catheterization system and discussed about the pros and cons of the developed system. The sixth and final chapter presents a conclusion and the scope of work which can be done in future to enhance the performance parameters and efficiency of the robotic cardiac catheterization system.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE SURVEY

The literature review forms the nucleus of all research. As a scientific investigation to succeed in new conclusions and establish facts, every analysis builds on existing knowledge. A literature review is exemplified as a survey of scientific books, published papers and articles, and other systematic scientific research sources relevant to a selected issue, scope of the study, and faculty of thought. The following content consists of studies performed to analyze the effects of radiation during cardiac catheterization, complications that occur during the procedure and accounts of published research on developed innovative robotic cardiac catheterization systems and clinical trials of such systems

2.1 Radiation Exposure During Cardiac Catheterization

Since the doctors started preferring minimally invasive surgical procedures like catheterization instead of the then conventional open-heart surgeries[1], radiation exposure has been one of the major issues that have been stuck along with the procedure. As the radiation leaked from the fluoroscope is harmful to the human body if absorbed in higher amounts. Several precautions are to be taken to prevent the operating physician from the harmful effects. Several studies including long term studies spanning over fifteen years with five thousand procedures per year and five years with fifteen thousand procedures [2] and short term studies have concluded that physicians performing multiple procedures over a period get 100-1000 times greater dosage than the patient. Studies have also shown that the x-ray radiation dosage absorbed by the operating physician is directly proportional to the dosage absorbed by the patient [3].

The amount of radiation absorbed by the primary operating physician is about 4-5 times greater than the secondary physician and the nursing staff [4]. And especially the nursing staff receive a very minuscule amount of radiation leaked through the fluoroscope. It was also observed that some factors affecting the absorbed radiation dosage are the height of the operating physician, the gender of the physician, and the professional superiority of the operating physician. Female physicians are observed to

absorb less dosage of x-ray radiation as compared to their male counterparts. Professional superiority is also accounted for in the factor affecting the absorption of radiation dosage as it has been revealed through many studies that physicians in training for the cardiac catheterization procedure often receive a higher amount of x-ray radiation as compared to their superior trainers [5]. The reason behind this situation is the lack of experience to perform a cardiac catheterization procedure efficiently and void of any mistakes which eventually leads to spending a longer duration of time under a fluoroscope as compared to the average time required for the procedure performed by a professional skilled and experienced physician.

The selection of the patient for the procedure is also a factor for an increase in radiation dosage for the physician. As the radiation exposure to the physician is directly proportional to the exposure to the patient, patient radiation exposure can be significantly influenced by a history of prior bypass surgeries and no. of target lesions [6]. Especially for angiographies and angioplasties, patients with multiple stents placements in the past are prone to complications during the surgery which eventually results into increased procedural time leading to prolonged duration of exposure to the x-ray radiation to the patient as well as the operating physician which can put the lung of the patient at risk.

Many studies conducted to analyze the effect of x-ray radiation through the fluoroscope for various procedures performed like valvuloplasty, angiography, hemodynamic monitoring, coronary angioplasty, electrophysiological ablation, etc. it was observed that radiation absorption by the physician during electrophysiological ablation is lower than the radiation absorbed during coronary angioplasty [7]. The reason mentioned for the difference in radiation dosage was due to the difference in the complexity of the procedures. It was seen that the procedure of coronary angioplasty often encounters complexities as compared to the procedure of electrophysiological ablation leading to an increase in procedural time. Another result obtained during the study was radiation dosage absorbed by the physician during the diagnostic procedure of angiography was also lower to the radiation dosage absorbed during interventional procedures like coronary angioplasty [8]. One of the studies has also shown that with the passage of time and advancement in technology, many procedures using cardiac catheterization has witnessed a decrease in fluoroscopic time because of better equipment and better safety features but one procedure, namely, Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI),

i.e. coronary angioplasty has seen a steep rise in procedural and fluoroscopic time. With the advancement in x-ray imaging devices and better catheter designs, more and more complexities in the procedures can be handled. Critical and risky areas are more accessible because of better visual aid. That is why these procedures started increasing the procedural time thus increasing the radiation dosage.

Many other studies were conducted to examine the effects of x-ray radiation on the parts of the body of an operating physician which are not covered by the protective shielding. The medical personnel often use the lead protective gear which primarily covers the torso and some part of the lower abdomen. The head shielding is like a skull cap that covers the forehead and upper skull. The results of these studies have often pointed out that firstly, the 0.5mm lead shield can attenuate 35% to 95% of the X-ray energies. And secondly, there are various other parts of the body like hands, neck, face which are left unprotected. The overexposure of the radiation can have genetic as well as somatic effects on the human body. The studies reveal that the wrists are most vulnerable to absorb the fluoroscopic x-ray radiation during the cardiac catheterization procedure. The left wrist receives a higher amount of radiation as compared to the right wrist as it is closer to the patient's body [9]. The second most part affected by the radiation is the eyes of the physician. Generally, there is no shielding for the eyes during the procedure which makes them even more susceptible to radiation absorption. Similar to the wrists, even the left eye gets more radiation dosage as compared to the right eye. The overall head radiation dosage is also greater than any part of the body. The third and last part which is often unshielded is the thyroid [10]. The thyroid also receives more radiation dosage than as specified by the radiography guidelines. Overall the order of parts defined by the amount of radiation absorbed can be represented as: Hands/Wrists > Hear/Eyes > Neck/ Thyroid > Trunk. The legs and lower part of the body receive a very minuscule amount of radiation as they are not directly exposed to the source of radiation.

The distance of the operating physician is also one of the factors influencing the radiation dosage. The farther the physician, the lower the dosage received. This is one of the main reasons why nursing and support staff are not so affected by the radiation. It has also been observed that the view of the heart also affects radiation exposure. If the physician is to the right side of the heart, he does experience higher exposure to the radiation than the left side. Some other factors like the catheter insertion site as well as

the working techniques of the operating physician also play a role in radiation absorption [11]. Some studies have shown that cardiac catheterization procedure performed through radial site results in a higher amount of radiation dosage received by the physician as compared to the femoral approach. As the x-ray radiation is focused at the chest of the patient and the femoral site is way too far from the region of exposed radiation, it created a safer environment than the radial site. The techniques adopted by the physicians also affect the radiation dosage as with proper technique and radiation protection training, the movements used, the placement of the body, the use of proper protection can help to decrease the exposure to radiation.

With time, several improvements in instruments were made and several advanced systems were adopted in service. For example, the thickness of the lead shielding has been changed from 0.5mm to 1mm which has significantly increased the amount of radiation absorbed by the protective gear and use of C-Arm fluoroscopes for better side angle composite vision is in practice [12]. But as per studies, these improvements also have several downsides to them. Like with an increase in size there was an increase in weight too, and because of the extra weight, the amount of stress experienced by the body of the physician has increased because of which the physicians and medical staff experience frequent fatigue. The disadvantage of using the C-Arm fluoroscope is that it has two to three times higher radiation leakage than the standard frontal projection.

Fig 2.1: Approximate localization of some in-room personnel during cardiac catheterization procedures[2].

Fig 2.2: Pattern in the (a) vertical plane and (b) horizontal plane of exposure values (mill roentgen per hour) during cardiac catheterization[11].

2.2 Complications of Cardiac Catheterization

Since the beginning of the use of surgical procedures in medicine, complications have been a part duly associated with the treatment [13]. And since cardiac catheterization is ultimately a surgical procedure, it also has a certain risk of complications occurring during the procedure as well as post-operation, often called 'post-op' complications. The studies conducted to assess the efficiency of the cardiac catheterization procedure also measured the risk of complications associated with the cardiac catheterization procedure [14]. Results of such studies showed that the overall rate of complications like myocardial infarctions etc. is around 1.9% and the mortality rate is around 2.6% during operation [15]. This means that out of every thousand patients undergoing

cardiac catheterization procedure, twenty-six patients die of complications. The complications occurring 48 hours prior to surgery and 24 hours post-surgery are called pseudo complications. The mortality rate for pre-surgery complications and post-surgery complications is 2.3% and 1.2% respectively [16]. The mortality rate for Percutaneous Coronary Intervention (PCI) is around 0.12% to 0.3%.

The complication rate is higher with greater risk patients and the inclusion of increasingly aged and acutely ill or unstable patients. During some studies, it was observed that congestive heart failure, Valvuloplasty, female gender, and percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty were significantly associated with the occurrence of vascular injuries [17]. So it was concluded from this study that an aggressive approach should be used for the obstruction even if the requirement of local vascular reconstruction arises. Several studies also observed that the occurring of deaths was much more frequent in children under the age of twelve months and the case of patients above sixty years of age [18][19].

In a study, over a period of two years observing around twelve thousand procedures which also included the one month follow-up after the procedure were observed that the overall complication rate was more for the therapeutic procedures like angioplasty as compared to diagnostic procedures like angiography [20]. The mortality rate was also found to be on a lower side in the case of the diagnostic procedure as compared to the therapeutic one. It was concluded from the study that even if the overall complication rate is low for cardiac catheterization, there is still scope to reduce the number of complications even further.

Fig 2.3: Graph depicting the incidence of complications of cardiac catheterization during the study period[20]

2.3 Robotic Catheterization System

The following are the accounts of groundwork done by researchers worldwide in designing and developing robotic cardiac catheterization systems and auxiliary systems associated with them:

M. Negoro et.al [21] designed a master-slave type robot-controlled catheterization system. The master-slave system is preferred for the drift of the catheter in forward, reverse, and rotational motion. The joystick works as the master system and has a very less mechanical impedance, which helps it convey exact orders from the operator. The controller, which acts as a slave device has the actuation control of the catheter. The master joystick is having two joints. The forward and reverse motion of the catheter is connected to the first joint and the rotational movement is related to the second joint of the master joystick. Both the joints are connected to the motor with a wire mechanism. No gears are present between the joints and the motor as it helps in reduction of the friction as well as backlash. An optical rotary encoder is attached to each joint. The resolution of the encoder is 1.6 micrometers per pulse and 0.023 degrees per pulse. In the slave device, the catheter is put between rollers, and the rollers are connected to the motors. There is a thin linear movement, the inner unit is hung from the outer shell with thin pillars. The outer shell rounds to get the rotating motion. Some strain gauges are placed on the thin pillars which measure the pushing component of the force between the catheter and the blood vessel. A micro force sensor is also installed on the tip of the catheter having diameter 1.2mm and a length of 5mm. It helps in measuring the contact force between the catheter tip and the blood vessel.

Wang et.al. [22] Designed and developed a novel procedure for robotic vascular interventional surgery (VIS). They developed a system having three technologies, mechanism control, image navigation, and haptic feedback force. In mechanism control, a master-slave structure was developed which can simulate the manual operations and achieve the axial and rotational movements. The robotic mechanism was divided into two parts; a supporting manipulator and a catheter navigator. The supporting manipulator had 5 DOF passive hydraulic mechanism. The surgeon manually adjusts the hydraulic manipulator to an appropriate position so that the catheter navigator is aligned to the vein. The axial translation of the catheters is implemented by a stepper motor driving two rollers. The rollers are adjustable so that

different kinds of catheters can be used, and when the robot is not being used, the surgeon can remove the catheter to switch to manual operation. The two rollers are fixed on a passive gear, which is driven by an active gear so that with actuation, the catheter is also rotated. The researchers also developed a system so that 3D representation of catheters and blood vessels can be generated using the 2D projection images and the catheter and vascular centerlines. Thirdly the researcher developed a miniature piezoelectric sensor that can be fixed on the catheter tip to detect the tactile forces between the catheter tip and the arterial wall. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) film is used as a microsensors to detect the contact force. This haptic feedback system was planned so that the vascular rupture can be kept off during the process.

Srimathveeravalli Govindarajan et.al.[23] designed a teleoperated haptically enabled system called “system for endovascular teleoperated access” (SETA). This system was capable of operating and manipulating the guidewires and catheters in the range of 0.014-0.13 inches. Some studies indicated that the speed of insertion as a function of time and the length of the guidewire inserted. The design was based on the data that 4.5N of axial force and 8Nm of torque is required for manipulating a 6F catheter. Also, the pinch pressure while handling the tool was measured as 76g of force. SETA’s slave mechanism was designed in two stages, first being to steer, insert, and withdraw the catheter and other to insert, withdraw, and rotate the guidewire. The linear actuator was made using friction wheels and the steering stage was made using a miniature gripper pulley combination. The traveling cart was designed using the pulley arrangement.

The friction pulley is beneficial over the lead screw-based and electromotive force based system as they provide infinite travel and do not suffer from the ripple effect. The friction rollers are made using two inch polyurethane coated wheels at shore hardness 55A and coefficient of friction 0.6 with polyethylene. Some provisions were provided on the frame for mounting tension springs to provide a non-slip gripping force on the tool as shown in fig 2.4. As buckling of the tool was a common occurrence in the procedure, a sufficient amount of reverse force was applied so that no buckling took place. The miniature gripper behaved like an axial bearing that transmitted power radially while allowing slip. The pulley arrangement was connected to a drive train having servo motors and torque sensors present.

The miniature gripper was assembled using two aluminum frames. Steel shafts were pressed through the frames and brass roller pins were mounted on the shaft. The shaft themselves were tension loaded using O-rings. The tension provided by the O-rings held the tool in place as it was being driven torsionally.

Fig 2.4: Operational principle of linear and rotational motion of the catheter[23]

Arai, Fumihito, et al.[24] designed a robotic catheterization based on a linear stepping mechanism. The mechanism was derived from the design of the mechanical pencil consisting of a ring and a gripper. The system was able to move in a forward direction; reverse direction as well as able to perform a rotational movement. As the mechanical pencil let the movement in one direction only, the mechanism was modified so that the movement was possible in both forward and reverse directions. When the catheter is moved forward and backward, the opening and closing of the point were shifted from one side to another and the grasping point of the ring was changed. For axial motion, ‘voice coil motor’ was used and a DC motor was used for the actuators that turn. An additional brake was also included in the actuation system so that no error in travel occurs. The travel of the catheter was controlled by the pulses given in the input to the actuator. The travel of the elongated component was about 1mm per pulse received by the actuator and the travel length was flexible and could be changed up to 10mm per pulse. The drawback of this system was that the accuracy of the travel of this system is very low. For the travel of 1mm per pulse, the actual travel of the catheter is anywhere between 0.3 to 1.9 mm. Some reasons for this inaccuracy were mentioned as being an insufficient grasping force, the deviation in the shape of the grasping point, shortage of force to the actuator and the inefficiency to determine the changing unit.

Guo, Shuxiang, et al.[25] developed a system to robotically manipulate the catheter in linear and rotational motion depicted in fig 2.5. The specialty of this design was that

the input to the system is not given electronically by the joystick but by a rather force sensing device in which the doctor uses a catheter on the input side such that the movement given by the doctor is sensed by the device and sent to the controller, which in turn actuates the actuator such that to replicate the same movement. Also, the system uses stepper motors for actuation and a force of 4N in axial grasping, and 6Nm for radial gripping torque was applied over the catheter. Also, the catheter used in this system had a fiber optic sensor attached to its tip which senses the impact or collision force between the catheter and the blood vessel. The force experienced by the fiber optic sensor was relayed to the catheter input device which in turn worked as an actual haptic force experienced by the doctor holding the actual catheter[26]. For axial motion, a lead screw assembly was used and for rotation, a pulley base rotation assembly was used which is mounted on the lead screw assembly. Both systems are actuated using the stepper motors.[27]

Fig 2.5: Catheter manipulator, the two degrees of freedom robotic device pulls, pushes and steers the patient catheter[25]

Irwin R. Barr [28] has developed a steerable catheter. This catheter does not require human or manual force to perform a turn or bend. The turning or bending of this catheter can be controlled electronically. The basic concept applied behind this invention is the movement of two bodies made of dissimilar material and having different thermal coefficients of expansion (TCE). If some heat is provided between these said materials, one will expand more than the other, hence achieving a turning movement. In this design, the inventor has introduced an additional Si rubber/plastic material over the PTFE material of the catheter. The Si/plastic is having a different coefficient of thermal

expansion than the PTFE material of the catheter. In-between these two, a resistance heater which provides the heat to both the materials. This assembly is termed as a reorientation device, which when placed on different sides of the catheter, will help to turn in that particular direction. When this bunch of reorientation device is placed on different locations on the catheter, it will work as a joint, i.e. turning movement from all those locations will be possible. According to the inventor, the TCE of the Si/plastic material must be about two to ten times the TCE of the catheter material. And the resistance heater wire used in an alloy of Ni:Co (80:20). In this invention, the inventor worked on the material level rather than the mechanical level.

The system is controlled by a joystick, which will be actuating some relays to conduct the electricity to the heating element but there is no real-time feedback from the catheter to the system. Cohen J Todd and Michael Seidenberg [29] has discussed the design and development of a system to operate an off the shelf steerable EP catheters like BLAZER II XP (Boston Scientific) SAFIRE and RF MARINR (Medtronic). The system provides a linear translation motion, rotational motion as well as the ability to manipulate the knob of the catheter which facilitates the movement of the distal tip.

This system is designed such that the handle of the catheter is attached inside a fitment such that the movement of the fitment moves with the movement of the system. As depicted in fig.2.6, the linear movement is provided by a lead screw-type of assembly which helps in forward and reverse motion of the catheter. The rotational motion is provided by a drum-like assembly inside which the catheter handle resides. The drum assembly works on the principle of friction rollers which are controlled by stepper motors. The movement of the distal tip is facilitated by the manipulation of the “knob” provided on the catheter. The angular displacement to the knob is facilitated with the help of a gear train mechanism. The feedback of the linear motion is sent to the controller by the proximity sensors attached along with the lead screw. The feedback to the rotational is provided by the sensor attached to the guiding roller.

Fig 2.6: Robotic catheter system by Cohen J Todd et.al [29]

Pivotto et.al.[30] have developed a device that can be used to operate the electrophysiological catheters. As the knob attached to the handle of this catheter facilitates the movement of the distal tip, the device is designed such that turning motion to that knob as well as overall Trans rotational motion to the catheter can be imparted. The device is having a large sled member upon which the catheter is placed. The handle of the catheter (with the knob) is fitted into a holder and placed upon the sled. This headrest on a platform base that is connected to the sled member by a lead screw as shown in fig 2.7.

The linear movement of the catheter handle (and the catheter itself) takes place due to the movement of the lead screw. The rotational movement of the catheter handle takes place due to the rotation of the head itself. A motor is attached to the head supported by the frame which helps the head to rotate coaxially with the longitudinal axis of the catheter. The movement of the end of the tip of the catheter is controlled by the knob present on the handle. Inside the head in which the handle is fitted, an assembly of parts is made which helps to turn that knob mechanically with the help of a motor and a slotted knob holder.

Fig 2.7: Lead screw-based catheter manipulator system by Pivotto et.al[30]

Dalia Beyar [31] has designed and developed an apparatus by which the guidewire, catheter and the ancillary instrument like angioplasty balloon can be fed into the vascular system. The apparatus which is called the “propelling device” by the inventor consist of a mechanical feeding system, as well as the controller for the feedback from the system and communication with the console. The catheter, guidewire, as well as the ancillary instrument, are treated the same as they all are cylindrical tube-like structure only varying in their diameters. The feeding mechanism consists of two sets of rollers, by which the catheter achieves forward motion as well as rotary motion as illustrated in fig 2.8. The first set of rollers are consisting of two wheels, among which, one is connected to a high precision stepper/servo motor via a slotted belt (to avoid slipping) and the other is free. The second set of rollers that provide rotary movement to the catheter has horizontal rotary rollers in which one is connected to a high precision stepper/servo motor via a slotted belt and the other is free similar to the first set. There are two torque gauge attached to each motor to monitor change in the feedback force, which may point towards some blockage in the path. Also, one rotor gauge is also present inside the system to measure the length of the catheter fed into the body. All the data from torque gauge and the rotary gauge is sent to the controller for processing. The controller shows the processed data on the console monitors and the system is controlled by a joystick attached to the console.

Fig 2.8: Catheter propelling device by Dalia Beyar[31]

M. Bret Schneider[32] has developed a design such that multiple elongated members such as Catheters and Guidewires and Balloon catheters can be handles simultaneously in the system. The design of the system consists of a module base, which is having two wheels attached to a plate. This plate can be rotated about the axis of the elongated members. A pulley belt system is attached to the support end of the plate to facilitate this movement. The system also consists of a drum, which is used to extend or retract the elongated members. The wheels are just provided to support the elongated members and prevent buckling during the movement. The drum is having a separately actuated wheel mounted on the drum, which is supposed to act as a spool for one of the elongated members such as a guidewire.

The wheel on the drum is positioned such that, when the drum rotates about its axis, with the help of a stepper motor, the wheel also moves over its body. As the catheter sheath will be attached to the drum and the guidewire will be attached to the wheel over the drum, the synchronous movement of these two elements will help to manipulate the positioning of the catheter or the guidewire. In a case where the catheter is to be withdrawn but the guidewire is to be unmoved, the drum will be rotated, so that the catheter is retracted. As the wheel is attached over the body of the drum, it will also move. But to keep the guidewire unmoved, the wheel will be actuated such that, it feeds the guidewire forward. So this relative motion of extension of the guidewire with the retraction of the catheter will give a situation such that the guidewire stays in its position while the catheter is being withdrawn.

Rafael Beyar et.al[33] have designed a mechanical transmission system for the catheter feeder mechanism. The system which is designed is a more compact, rigid, and mechanically reliable system compared to the present ones. This complex mechanical structure as depicted in fig 2.9, consists of two large gears, namely gear 1 and gear 2. Gear 2 is mounted on gear 1 but is independent of its movement. Both of the main gears are driven by their respective drive screws, connected to a drive shaft which is eventually connected to their respective motors. The linear movement of the catheter is controlled by the movement of two rollers, one of which is connected to the roller drive gear, which is eventually meshed with gear 2. The second roller is free to roll and is connected to a spring-loaded arm to maintain the friction for a smooth motion between the catheter and the rollers. This whole roller assembly is rigidly attached to gear 1. The movement of gear 2 gives the catheter a linear motion and the motion of gear 1 rotated the whole roller assembly which eventually rotates the catheter about its longitudinal axis. There are two additional rollers present after the main rollers to provide the positional transmission data to the encoder. The drive shaft connected to the motor is also connected to the encoder. Data from both of these devices helps in making it a closed-loop system.

Fig 2.9: Mechanical transmission system for the catheter feeding mechanism by Rafael Beyar et.al[33]

Wallace et.al [34] developed a system intending to impart rotational and translation motion to the medical steerable catheter. They designed this system such that the translation motion is achieved by a sliding carriage type mechanism. The slider is placed upon a base structure and the slidable mounting is accomplished by high precision linear bearings. The motion is transferred to the carriage from a motor with the help of an intricate pulley belt mechanism. This helps in a synchronized relative motion to be imparted on the carriage. The carriage on top of itself carries the gripper which holds the catheter in place.

The rotation to the system is imparted by a rotatably mounted instrument driver over an instrument base. The rotation between the instrument driver and the instrument base is facilitated by a heavy-duty flanged bearing structure. This configuration allows the system to rotate about the approximate axis of the catheter. The rotation assembly having a roll cable loop is mounted upon a roll motor as shown in fig 2.10. The actuation of this roll motor interacts with the friction surface of the roll loop and the motion or displacement takes place. The drawback of this axial and rotational system is that it is not able to provide infinite travel to the catheter. The limitation of the axial travel is approximately equal to the span of the base and the limitation of the angular displacement is about 180° as the roll loop design is not circular.

Fig 2.10: Rotation assembly of instrument driver by Wallace et.al[34]

Kokish et.al.[35] have designed a novel mechanism that can be used to impart translation as well as the rotary motion to an elongated medical device such as a catheter or guidewire. The system is designed such that the member which comes in direct contact of the elongated device is disposable which makes this system a perfect fit to be used in a medical environment. The axial motion is imparted by two rollers wheel which is meshed with each other by 2 spur gears. The motion to the roller wheels is transferred to them by a worm gear which in-turn is getting its motion because of a planetary gear assembly. The rotary motion is provided to the disposable drive apparatus by a system of 3 external cylindrical rollers in which the only one is driving roller and the other two are just support rollers. The axial motion drive apparatus is enclosed in a cylindrical shell-like structure which gives the external rollers a surface to interact. This interaction is what causes the motion to occur. This drive system is designed such that the linear or translator motion, as well as the rotary motion of the elongated member, can be done independently as well as simultaneously.

Tal Wenderow et.al [36] with Corindus robotics has developed a remotely controlled robotic catheter system for performing interventional procedures. The system developed consists of a catheter drive cassette configured to be coupled with a motor driving base. The system is called a bedside system. The primary focus of this patent is on the design and development of the catheter drive cassette. The cassette is a removable, one-time use, catheter driving device which provides a linear as well as the rotational motion to the guidewire. The cassette which comes in direct contact with the guidewire needs to be sterile at all times, so the cassette is designed such that it is to be used only once. The cassette rest upon a motor drive base, which provides support as well as motion input to the cassette. The cassette is connected to the motor driver base by 3 capstans and capstan sockets such that they facilitate alignment with the motor base.

The cassette is having 3 drive mechanisms, namely axial drive mechanism, rotational drive mechanism, and second axial drive mechanism. The axial drive mechanism helps to move the guidewire in forward and reverse direction and the rotational drive helps facilitate the rotation of the guidewire. The second axial drive mechanism helps in the linear movement of the working catheter (the one with a balloon and stent). There are several embodiments of the system mentioned in the filed patent.in some cases, the axial driving mechanism of the guidewire in on the front side of the rotational drive (i.e.

near to the human body) and in some cases, it is on the lateral end of the rotational drive. The axial drive consists of a pair of rollers, or a roller and a friction surface or a pair of friction belts depending on the embodiment.

The rollers which are present in pairs are a combination of one driving and one idle rotating pair. The idle rollers are spring-loaded which helps them in maintaining enough force which will facilitate the movement of the guidewire due to friction. The same thing goes with the rotational drive too. But here, both the rollers are idle and just for providing support during the linear movement. In the rotational drive, there are two supports present inside which the rotating drive resides. The rotational drive is rotated with the help of gear and pinion mechanism. The rollers inside the rotation drive provide enough frictional torque which helps to rotate the guidewire.

The second axial drive mechanism just facilitates the linear movement of the working catheter and not rotation. The second axial drive mechanism feeds the working catheter into a “y-connector” which helps it to follow the guidewire inside the human body. This patent deals with only the design and construction of different embodiments of the remote catheter system and does not include an electrical or control part of the system. They have also discussed the idea of “variable Drive Torque” for the axial drive mechanism of the guidewire feeding system.[37] The variable drive torque can be given to the axial rollers of the axial drive mechanism by controlling the motor. In all the other devices, the motor was only able to control the velocity of the axial rollers but here there is a provision that the torque implied on that rollers can also be changed.

In addition to that, they have claimed to develop a control workstation for the remotely controlled robot-assisted percutaneous intervention device. The control system controls the movement of the PCI device along at least two degrees of freedom. It also includes a graphical interface that displays icons that shows the operational status of each of the PCI devices.[38] The controls include a touch screen, a catheter control, a guidewire control, and a working catheter control. The joysticks allow the user to advance, retract, and rotate the components. The guidewire and the guide catheter have 2 controls for translation and rotation while the working catheter is having the control of only translation. The position of guide catheter control is far on left, guidewire control joystick is in the middle, and working catheter joystick is on the far right. Similar to the joysticks the positioning of the controls on the touchscreen is in the same order. The

touchscreen is also having one extra option of express retraction of the guidewire which facilitates the pulling out of the guidewire from the body at a very high rate after the procedure is complete.

Zirps et.al. [39] have focused on the driving mechanism of the guidewire in forward, reverse, and rotational motion. For forward and reverse motion, the system is having an axial drive system in which the guidewire is moved along its axis with the help of a pair of rollers in which one pair of roller wheels are driving wheels connected to the motor and one set of the wheels are idler. The wheels provided in the axial drive have slits to increase the ability of the wheel to grip and impart better axial motion to the guidewire. The slits basically provide better friction when engaged to the surface of the guidewire. The rotational part of the motion is provided by the rotational drive where which is driven by bevel gear connected to a motor. The wheels in the rotational assembly do not necessarily have the texture or the slits and there is a groove on the wheels of the rotational side to extend the area of contact for better gripping.

2.4 Comparison and Clinical Trials of Robotic Catheterization Platforms

With the invention and development of newer robotic catheterization systems, various studies were conducted to compare the platforms as well as analyze the safety, working ability as well as the efficiency of the developed robotic catheterization system.[40] One such study was conducted to compare the manual cardiac catheterization procedure with the robot-assisted cardiac catheterization procedure [41]. For this study, a silicon-based transparent CT-reconstructed anthropomorphic phantom representing a thoracoabdominal aneurysm was used. The phantom was filled with a blood mimicking water glycerol mixture and circulated using a pulsating blood pump. For this study, a Sensei X system from Hansen medicals was used. The system used a steerable guide catheter (Artisan) for the study. On similar lines, another study was conducted to compare conventional endovascular procedure and robotic endovascular procedure in aortic aneurysm repair [42]. The robotic study part was done using the “Magellan robotic endovascular system, manufactured by Hansen Medicals, Inc.” (fig 2.11). The system uses a steerable electromechanical catheter system which is controlled by a ‘master-slave’ mechanism. The guiding is done by the 3- dimensional hand-operated

joystick system present at the workstation. The inner guidewire has a 270-degree bend radius inside the unidirectional outer guide sheath.

The result of these studies showed that the median procedure time for the cannulation by the robotic method was significantly lower than the time taken through the manual procedure. Also, the total number of movements required for the procedure was approximately 10 times lesser for the robot-assisted procedure as compared to the manual procedure.

Fig 2.11: “Magellan robotic endovascular system, manufactured by Hansen Medical, USA” used to conduct the study by Au, Stephanie et.al[43]

the study also points out some disadvantages of the robotic system as it lacks the mechanical feedback that the operator receives from the manual catheter manipulation and hence the ability to assess the amount of force that is being applied to the target tissue, which may increase the chance of vascular injuries and punctures. The study also states that the setup time of the robotic procedure is approximately fifteen minutes as the setup time for the conventional procedure is negligible. Steerable robotic catheters with intuitive control may overcome some of the limitations of standard catheters. This study also highlighted the limitations of the robotic catheterization system as firstly being the cost. The initial investment cost is around US\$600,000 with maintenance fees of US\$60,000-80,000 per year[44]. Secondly, some special adjustments are to be made in the operating room to accommodate the robotic endovascular system [45].

Another study comparing the current contemporary robotic cardiac catheterization systems was conducted on multiple aspects such as instrumentation and ergonomics, skill assessment, endovascular imaging and navigation techniques, robotic

catheterization platforms, and human-robot interaction. In instrumentation, it was discussed about the types of steerable catheters which are available namely, magnetic type, pull wire type, smart material actuated, and hydraulic drive type. One of the outcomes of the study was that It was safer to use a magnetically controlled catheter as they have a soft tip which reduces the risk of damage to the tissues. It was also seen that The smart material type catheters have shape memory alloy (SMA) whose elastic properties vary with change in temperature, allowing bending and deflection of the catheter tip by heating or cooling the SMA actuator. Also, For the haptic response, the study discusses fiber optic-based force sensors such as ‘TactiCath’ and the piezoelectric based sensors like PVDF polymers. While comparing the robotic catheterization platform, the study took ‘Sensei X’ and ‘Magellan’ of Hansel medicals, ‘Amigo’ of Catheter robotics (fig 2.12), and ‘CorPath 200’ of Corindus Vascular Robotics[46].

The sensei X uses the distal force measurement system ‘IntelliSense which provides a visual display of forces and tactile vibration.[47] The Magellan however does not provide force feedback and the guidance is achieved only in 2D using fluoroscope imaging. The amigo system catheter uses the steerable standard commercial mapping catheter having 3DOF at the tip[48]. The CorPath 200 is another remote-controlled system which uses the over the counter non-steerable catheter.[49] [50]

Fig 2.12: “Amigo” robotic catheter of ‘Catheter robotics, USA’ used in the study by Rafii-Tari et.al.[51]

For assessing the feasibility, accessibility, and efficiency of developed innovative robotic catheterization systems, studies were conducted covering the clinical trials of the systems. The following are the accounts of such clinical trials conducted with the robotic catheterization platforms:

B Rafael, et al. [52] conducted a clinical study upon the use of a remote navigation system designed by Rafael Beyar et al. The study was performed by observing eighteen

patients undergoing the PCI procedure using the catheter remote navigation system. Out of eighteen cases, seventeen times the guidewire was successful in navigating through the lesions, and fifteen times the system was successful in delivering stents. Ten patients were treated by direct stenting and in five patients high pressure after stent dilation was performed. All patients were treated with a single stent and two patients were delivered with multistents because of incomplete lesion coverage. No MACE (major adverse cardiovascular events) during the procedure were seen.

Cercenelli, Marcelli et.al. [53][54] conducted an experimental study on animals to test the average time taken for the catheterization procedure done manually as well as using a remote catheterization procedure. In this study, the robotic system used was developed by Cercenelli et.al and it consists of an electrophysiology catheter and a robotic hand. This whole system was called a 'telerobotic system'. This telerobotic system was able to reposition the catheter in a linear direction as well as in rotational orientation. The experimentation was done on 3 adult female sheep. The introduction of the catheter and providing the incision in the animal skin and vein as well as the advancement of the catheter to the right atrium was done manually. After the navigation and repositioning within the cardiac chamber were done robotically. The statistical analysis showed that the time taken to perform the procedure by the telerobotic system was significantly lower than the time taken to do the same procedure manually. The tip of the catheter equipped with force sensors that provided safe navigation to the standard EP catheter. The remote navigation was achieved at all targets and the force sensor indicated reliable information about catheter endocardium contact. The repositioning time was reduced by more than half in robotic procedures as compared to the manual procedure.

Fig 2.13: Animal trials conducted by Marcelli et.al[54]

Weisz, Giora, et al. [55] conducted a study to evaluate the safety as well as technical and clinical efficiency of robot-assisted PCI. This study was conducted on one hundred and sixty-four patients at nine different locations by twenty-three different operators. The robotic system used to perform percutaneous coronary interventions was “CorPath 200” manufactured by Corindus, USA (fig 2.14). All the procedures were performed via femoral arterial access with a 6F guiding catheter. The PCI procedures were successfully completed in all the patients without conversion to the manual and technical success of the device was achieved in one hundred sixty-two of one hundred sixty-four patients where no device-related complications were found[56]. The clinical procedure rate of success was one hundred sixty out of one hundred sixty-four where four patients suffered non Q wave myocardial infarctions. No deaths, strokes or myocardial infarctions or revascularization occurred in the 30-day period after the procedure. the radiation exposure to the primary operator was recorded at 95.2% lower than the average level found at the traditional table position.[57]

Fig 2.14: Robotic device “CorPath 200” manufactured by “Corindus Vascular robotics, USA” used in conducting the study by Weisz, Giora, et.al[58]

This chapter covered some documented accounts of studies and patented research done on various topics such as effects of radiation on medical personnel during cardiac catheterization, complications involved with the manual cardiac catheterization procedure, various accounts of robotic systems for cardiac catheterization developed by researchers across globe and studies involving clinical trials of some of the robotic cardiac catheterization devices on animals as well as humans for analyzing the effectiveness and feasibility of cardiac catheterization procedures performed robotically.

CHAPTER 3: PROBLEM FORMULATION AND HYPOTHESIS

The procedure of cardiac catheterization is minimally invasive where a thin tubular structure called catheter is threaded inside the vascular system of the human body to reach its targeted location. It is one of the leading techniques for the diagnosis and treatment of heart-related diseases. As compared to other treatment procedures for cardiovascular diseases such as open-heart surgery, one distinctive feature in cardiac catheterization is that it cannot be tracked directly or with a naked eye. To track the movement of the catheter, an X-ray imaging device called fluoroscope has to be necessarily used. This fluoroscopic radiation is absorbed in a high amount can be highly noxious to the physician performing the procedure. The protective clothing which the physician wears can also induce several musculoskeletal complications such as spondylitis and so on. Also, there is a very limited number of such robotic catheterization systems available commercially and none of them is indigenously developed. So to avoid all these adversities, a novel indigenous developed robotic cardiac catheterization system was envisioned.

While developing the robotic cardiac catheterization system, several challenges are to be identified ahead of time such that during the development phase, solutions for all these challenges can be established. The first and foremost challenge is to impart motion to the catheter. The catheter must be imparted with a linear as well as a rotational movement. For this to be facilitated, a 2- DoF driving mechanism for the robotic catheterization system has to be developed. Secondly, it was very necessary to analyze as what are the physical limitations of the catheter such that those are not to be exceeded during the time of operation. It may include the amount of force required to deform the catheter plastically or what will be the range of applied load such that the catheter may not change its shape or deform in any manner. To ensure all these a static structural analysis on the catheter has to be performed to get evident results for all such parameters.

The third challenge, the most important challenge is to design the robotic system such that it maintains the standard of sterility required in the field of medicine. Sterility is a major factor in any surgery or similar procedure in medicine and any sort of negligence

can cost a patient's life due to an infection or any other complication. So after considering all the conditions, the robotic system must have either replaceable parts or must have the ability to be sterilized. There are some other challenges in the mechanical design of the robotic system. The catheter driving mechanism must not restrict the travel of the catheter to a specific length or a specific angle. There should be no dimensional limitations for the operation of the catheter. The robotic system must also be sensitive and precise enough such that no overshoot or no overturn of the catheter must take place.

Hypothesis

Therefore, after considering all the challenges and conditions mentioned above, it can be hypothesized that a linear motion and a rotational motion can be imparted on to a catheter by using a 2-DoF driving mechanism of a robotic cardiac catheterization system. It can also be hypothesized that the physical limitations of a catheter can be identified by performing a static structural analysis on the catheter using the Finite Element Method. And finally, it can be hypothesized that a dynamic relationship can also be established between the force responsible for imparting motion to the catheter and the physical parameters of the drive components.

CHAPTER 4: DESIGN EVOLUTION

4.1 2-DoF Mechanism for Catheter motion

Design is a tool for realizing an idea, concept, or theory into a drawing, plan, specification, etc such that it ultimately allows to achieve or resolve a series of desired objectives. The primary objective of a robotic catheterization system is to replicate the linear motion and rotational motions performed by the operating physician manually. The drive system was designed with the objective to provide axial motion and rotational motion to the catheter. The preliminary idea of designing the drive mechanism was to impart both the motions simultaneously, but with subsequent developments and implication of different motion imparting systems, two independent drive mechanisms for axial and rotational motion respectively were conceptualized. The following are the accounts of the evolution of the design of the driving mechanism for robotic catheterization system:

4.1.1. Reverse Lead Screw Mechanism

This design was one of the first iterations in the sequence of evolution of the system. This design was conceptualized to facilitate the simultaneous linear as well as rotational movements of the catheter. as per the design, the catheter is supposed to be fixed in the catheter holder which is a cavity specially designed as per the shape of the catheter head. This system is designed such that only linear actuators like pneumatic or hydraulic pistons, rack and pinion mechanism are required for imparting the motion. The transfer of motion from the linear actuators to the system will be carried out by the actuation handles as shown in the figure. The rotating screw and the sleeve are having screw threads on their surfaces such that when the sleeve is moved in a forward direction, it will rotate the rotating screw eventually rotating the catheter. the sleeve and rotating screw slide over a sliding base which gives it support as well as a frictionless surface for smooth movements. The relative displacement of the actuators attached to the actuation handles will determine the amount and type of motion imparted over the system. If the displacement of the linear and rotational actuation handle is the same, then the resultant movement of the catheter will be only linear.

In this case, no rotational movement will be experienced by the catheter; and if a linear displacement is given to the rotational actuator handle while the linear actuation handle is kept stationary, the only pure rotational movement will be experienced by the catheter without any linear displacement. But if the actuator handles are given unequal linear displacements, then a combination of rotational and translational motion will be experienced by the catheter.

Fig 4.1: Labelled diagram of reverse lead screw mechanism

The main drawback of this system was the limitation on the span of travel for the catheter. The maximum travel of the catheter was bound with the dimension of the sliding base as well as the actuation travel length or the maximum displacement of the actuator. The actuator was not able to move linearly beyond a certain distance during operation. The same goes for the number of possible rotations too. The maximum number of possible rotations are bound with the physical dimensions as well as the pitch of the sleeve and rotating screw. The number of possible subsequent turns available for the catheter were limited. So this design put a cap on the maximum continuous single direction travel of the catheter as well as the number of turns available for the catheter and had no provision to exceed those limits if such a need ever arises.

4.1.2. Geared Mechanism

This design is the second iteration in the sequence of evolution of the system. This design was also created such that only one unit is required for achieving the translational as well as the rotational motion for the catheter. In this design, the type of actuators required for actuating the system is strictly rotational as shown in the figure. In this design, the catheter head is to be placed inside the catheter holder, which is a concentric cylindrical structure present inside the main body. The catheter holder can rotate with the help of the spur gear assembly. The stepper motor attached to the gear drives the catheter holder in a clockwise and counter-clockwise direction. This will eventually rotate the catheter. The linear motion is transferred to the catheter by the rack and pinion mechanism attached to the body. The linear motion of the whole body will impart the linear motion to the catheter. The body is supported on a slider base (not shown). The benefit of this design over the previous one is that the catheter can be moved with precision in very small steps. The sensitivity of this device can be changed by changing the gear ratio in the linear as well as the rotational drive system. Increase or decrease in the number of teeth in the axial pinion gear of the linear motion drive can facilitate to improve the precision in the movement of the linear drive but the same cannot be done with the rotational drive as both the gears will have to be changed instead of only one as in the case of the linear drive.

Fig 4.2: Labelled diagram of a geared mechanism

The disadvantage of this design is the same as that of its predecessor. As it can provide an infinite number of turns during the rotation of the catheter, it cannot be done in the case of linear movement. The maximum linear displacement of this system is totally dependent on the dimensions of the rack which is attached to the body. This system can have a total linear displacement of twice the length of the rack. And no further extension of length is possible if the need ever arises. As this system is heavily dependent on gears, the factor of inaccuracy because of backlash occurring in the gears will affect the precision in linear as well as rotational movements.

4.1.3. Frictional Slab Axial Drive

Fig 4.3: Labelled diagram of frictional slab axial drive

This design is the third iteration in the series of the evolution of the system. At this stage, it was decided to design two separate drive mechanisms for linear/axial motion and rotational motion. The complete system was termed as a “composite drive system” of which this is the design of the mechanism which will facilitate the axial or linear movement of the catheter. In this design, the catheter head will not be fastened on reinforcement as in previous figures. Here the catheter tip will be inserted into the drive through the catheter guide hole and the catheter will pass in between the rollers and the support slab. The actuator, a stepper motor will be connected to the gear train over which the rollers are attached. The rollers will be in direct contact with the catheter. The rollers are having grooves in them so that the catheter will be gripped more properly

during the travel of the catheter. The gear ratio is kept 1:1 between the drive gear and the gear attached to the rollers. The support slab present on the opposite side of the rollers will help in pushing down the catheter over the rollers and provide enough force for the friction to come into play and provide motion to the catheter.

The vantage of this scheme is that it is capable to provide infinite travel to the catheter in the axial direction and the translation of the catheter is not limited by the dimensions of the system. The slidable support slab connected to the springs facilitates two things, firstly to impart the external force over the catheter such that the friction is achieved between the rolls and the catheters, and secondly, it gives the extrinsic backing to the catheter such that no buckling of the catheter takes place during the axial thrust. The catheter guide holes provided in the system have another task instead of simply allowing the catheter to just pass through it, they are stationed at that location such that no upward movement (normal to the base) of the catheter must take place during the operation.

The downside to this design is that the support slab has its wide front face in direct touch with the catheter during the performance of this drive system and because of that the catheter goes through an unnecessarily large amount of friction while moving through this scheme. This extra friction has to be compensated by offering a more driving force to the catheter, which ultimately involves unnecessary heating of the catheter and power loss.

4.1.4. Double Roller Axial Drive

This design is the fourth iteration in the evolution of the system and the second iteration in the design of the axial drive. The design is similar to its predecessor in terms of the basic principles. The motion to the catheter will be imparted by the driving rollers, which are connected to the spur gear which are meshed with the driving. The actuator is a stepper motor connected to the driving gear. The motion provided by the actuator will be directly transferred to the driving rollers. In this design, the support slab is substituted by a pair of idle rollers. These rollers will work the same way as the support slab did but with added benefits. The redundant friction experienced by the catheter during the previous design was eliminated by the introduction of these idle rollers as the working surface of these idle rollers only make point contact instead of a full line

contact as in the case of the support slab. Therefore, no extra friction is experienced by the catheter. and because the idle rollers also rotate during the movement it helps in smoother travel of the catheter and prevents the extra power consumed because of the rubbing of the catheter over the slab surface. The placement of bearings inside the idle rollers will facilitate even smoother travel for the catheter. the catheter guide hole is replaced with a catheter guide slot such that easy change of catheter during the procedure can be facilitated.

Fig 4.4: Labelled diagram of double roller axial drive

The only drawback to the system is that the force applied by the springs onto the slider platform is directly transmitted on to the catheter by only two points of contacts which results in the experience of concentrated force over two points rather than the distributed force over the entire surface . This concentrated load may happen to deform the rather flexible catheter. This distortion will not impede the operation of the movement of the catheter but if the deformation is not restored automatically by the catheter, then in some applications like hemodynamic monitoring, it may make a problem. The other minuscule problem which can be ruled out by further refining the design is about the backlash because of the gear tooth profile. Even if the backlash is real small; it will be a definite reason for the inaccuracy and dilution in the precision of the system.

4.1.5. Double Set Rotational Drive

Fig 4.5: Labelled diagram of double set rotational drive

This is the first iteration of the rotational drive for the composite drive mechanism. This mechanism will facilitate the rotational movement of the catheter inside the human body. The principle of operation of this device is fairly similar to the axial drive of the system. In this design, the catheter is pinched between the supporting idle rollers. These rollers are on actuated and are present just to grip the catheter such that when the assembly rotates, the catheter must rotate with it. The tension springs provided in the drive apply force on the slider, which eventually transfers the force onto the catheter via the idle rollers. The axis of rotation near coincides with the axis of the catheter. The idle rollers not only provide the pinching force but also facilitate the smooth axial travel of the catheter. The drive is to be actuated using a stepper motor, which will be coupled to the drive via either a planetary gear train or by Schmidt coupling, both of which facilitate the transfer of rotation to parallel axis shafts. The only limitation of the design of this drive is that the components including the spring, the slider, and the rollers take so much space such that in order to rotate the whole assembly, a very big turning space is required. This big space unnecessarily increases the total dimension of the device and eventually increases the weight of the rotational drive which will affect the requirement of torque to rotate the assembly.

4.1.6. Single Set Rotational Drive:

Fig 4.6: Labelled diagram of single set rotational drive

This is the second iteration of the rotational drive for the composite drive mechanism. This drive system mostly addresses the shortcomings of its predecessors. This rotational drive system is smaller in dimension, compensating one of the limitations of its predecessor which was its size. The reduction in size was possible due to the use of smaller rollers as well as reducing the number of roller pairs. The first iteration of the rotational drive had six pairs of inactive rollers whereas it has only four pairs of rollers. Subsequently number of springs were also reduced from eight to four. The spring force helps rollers grip the catheter. An additional transparent lid is also included in the design for maintaining proper sterility during the procedure. The catheter insertion slots provided in the drive will ensure easy insertion and removal of the catheter before the procedure and also in the case of an emergency switch to manual. The drive can provide an infinite number of turns in a clockwise and anticlockwise direction to the catheter irrespective of the design dimensions. This rotational drive system will be actuated using a dc stepper motor and a belt pulley drive mechanism. One of the limitations of this subassembly is that it does not have bearings attached with the rollers as bearings for such small and intricate dimensions are not available. All the other shortcomings of the predecessor drive like increased weight and large torque requirements have also been nullified in this drive design.

4.1.7. Robotic System Assembly

Fig 4.7: Labelled diagram of robotic assembly

The design of this system is the combination of the axial drive and the rotational drive. As shown in the figure, the axial drive is situated ahead of the rotational drive in the forward direction of motion of the catheter. Tip of the catheter will be passing through the axial drive into the catheter guide to which a guiding sheath is attached. This guiding sheath will be present from the catheter guide until the introduces sheath present at the point of entry into the human body.

The guiding sheath will help prevent buckling of the catheter while traveling from the robotic system to the insertion point of the human body. As mentioned previously, the catheter will be clamped inside the rotational drive which will be imparting the rotational motion to the catheter, and then it will be passing through the axial drive which will impart the linear motion i.e. motion in forward and reverse direction upon the catheter. the catheter guide is just a supporting structure that will facilitate the insertion of the catheter inside the catheter guiding sheath.

The axial drive and the rotational drive are attached to the actuator casing inside which the actuators i.e. the stepper motors are placed. The axial drive is placed over the flat surface of the actuator casing. The transfer of motion from the actuator to the driving gear of the axial drive will be enabled by specially designed couplings connecting motor shaft with the gear shaft, which are placed inside the actuator casing (not shown).

In the axial drive, the motion is primarily transferred from the stepper motor to the driving gear. The specially designed coupling will be ensuring that the no slippage takes place and motor torque is fully transferred onto the driving gear. The driving gear is connected with two spur gears as shown in fig 4.4. the gear ration between driving gear and the spur gear is 1:1, therefore theoretically all the torque received by the driving gear from the motor will be transferred to the spur gears. As per the gearing laws of motion, the spur gears will be rotating in the reverse direction to that of the driving gear. And the rollers attached over the spur gears are fixed, the speed of rotation of the rollers will be exactly similar to the speed of rotation of spur gear. With all the gear mechanism involved, the speed of rotation of the rollers will be equal to the speed of rotation of the actuating motor.

The rotational drive is enabled to rotate freely into the scooped out groove of the actuator casing and will be supported by a pair of pedestal/support bearings on either side. As mentioned before, the axis of rotation of the rotational drive will be in the vicinity of the longitudinal axis of the catheter. The method of transfer of rotation of motion for the rear rotational drive is with the help of a belt and pulley mechanism. A 16mm pulley with 8mm bore has been used both sides on the motor shaft as well as driveshaft connected via a friction belt of appropriate size and tension. Similar to the axial driving mechanism, the speed and torque provided by the actuating motor will be directly transferred to the rotational assembly. The rotating speed and angular displacement of the rotating assembly will be the same as to the speed and angular displacement of the actuating motor shaft.

The shortcomings of the previous designs related to sterility as well as dimensional adversity have been accommodated through this design by the inclusion of protective lid on the axial drive as well as the rotational drive which will ensure procedural sterility, that it no external interference will be associated during the operation of the system. The catheter guiding sheath and the support have also been modified such that the catheter can be removed from the support easily if the need for manual conversion ever arises. The interchangeability of the components has also been modified such that for each procedure, new fresh components can be used every time for a new procedure to ensure sterility.

4.2 Catheter Modeling

The first use of catheters dates back to 1929 where Dr. Werner Forssmann used a rubber catheter to perform minimally invasive surgery. In that procedure, a rubber catheter was used. Since then, with the advancement in technology and with a lot of research different types of catheters were developed for different procedures specializing in fulfilling the need for the procedure. Majorly cardiac catheters are divided into 2 main groups, diagnostic catheters, and guide catheters. Diagnostic catheters are used for the procedures like Angiography, Pressure Monitoring, and Oxygen saturation monitoring, etc. the guide catheters are used in the procedures like angioplasty, where the catheter need to carry a guidewire as well as a stent catheter, in valvuloplasty procedures where an inflatable balloon catheter is carried through the guide catheter. The specification of diagnostic catheters includes a thicker shaft, small inner diameter, tapering tip, and two-layer reinforcement. The physical specifications of guide catheters include a thinner shaft, large internal diameter, non-tapering tip, and a three-layer reinforcement.

The size of the catheters is measured based on the “French Catheter Scale”. The French catheter scale is considerably used to measure the outer diameter of all cylindrical medical instruments. According to the scale,

$$\text{Outer Diameter (mm)} = \frac{Fr}{3}$$

The parts of a catheter are the tip length, primary curve, secondary curve, tertiary curve, and the catheter length as shown in fig 4.8 and fig 4.9. The increase in tip length provides more stability in the target vessel but by compromising maneuverability in the parent vessel. The primary curve adjusts the angle of the target vessel from the parent vessel. The secondary curve works in the width of the parent artery. The tertiary vessel is always placed normally to the curvature of the parent artery and the catheter length is chosen depending on the patient.

Fig 4.8: Parts of a catheter[59]

Fig 4.9: Diagram depicting sections of a catheter

A: Tip Length, **B:** Primary curve, **C:** Secondary length, **D:** Tertiary length, **E:** Catheter length

The ideal characteristics of a catheter consist of:

- better torque control: for precise turning movements
- pushability: for precise linear movement
- flexibility: to bend freely in required positions
- trackability: ability to follow the desired path
- radio-opacity: visibility on the fluoroscope
- atraumatic tip: to not cause trauma to inner walls of the blood vessel
- low surface frictional resistance: to provide smoother travel to the catheter
- kink resistance: to avoid kink during the procedure

By comparing the wall thickness of the catheters, it can be observed that the thick wall catheters are having a better push and torque transmission. And the thin wall catheters help in improved monitoring, blood sampling, and flushing abilities but with less torque maintaining ability and inability to sustain high-pressure injection.

The common materials generally used for manufacturing catheters are Polyethylene terephthalate also commonly known as “Dacron”, Nylon-12, Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) and Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) which is commonly called “Teflon”. For

better radio-opacity, Barium (Ba), Bismuth (Bi), and Iridium (Ir) are introduced in the mixture. The catheter made of Dacron is very maneuverable and flexible. Nylon-12 gives a great physical and mechanical strength to the catheter with reduced friction and the ability to achieve a large flow rate of fluids. Polyurethane has excellent shape memory and is way softer than Polyethylene or PTFE, so it causes very little vascular trauma. Poly Vinyl Chloride is softest and most flexible among all the contemporary materials. But on the downside, it has a high friction coefficient, very poor memory and it is also hydrophilic. Polytetrafluoroethylene or Teflon has a very low coefficient of friction, which enables it for a very smooth and atraumatic movement inside the vessels. But on the negative side, PTFE is the stiffest among all and have very poor shape memory. That is why nowadays Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) is applied as a coating over Nylon or Polyurethane catheters to reduce the friction during movement inside the vascular system of the human body. As depicted in fig 4.10 below, the catheter has three layers. The outermost layer is a coating (commonly PTFE) for reducing the thrombogenicity and friction. The outer layer is made of one or a mixture of the materials mentioned above such as Nylon, Polyurethane, or a combination of such materials. And in the middle is the reinforcement mesh commonly made of stainless steel which helps in kink resistance as well as helps reducing twisting or buckling during the operation.

Fig 4.10: Components of a catheter[60]

4.2.1 Dimensioning and measuring the catheter

To analyze the behavior of the catheter under certain force conditions like a fracture, deformation, etc., a CAD model of the catheter was needed. By using a CAD model and analysis software using Finite Element Analysis (FEA), we can determine the outcomes of such conditions virtually. In doing so, the first step is to create a replica of the catheter in the virtual domain using software like Dassault CATIA V5, SOLIDWORKS, etc. for creating any model in CAD software, the main requisite knowledge is about the structure, composition and the dimensions of the component like length, width, radius, tapering angle, etc. for our analysis, we replicated a 5F diagnostic catheter. In doing so, a “Cordis INFINITY 5F Diagnostic Catheter” was taken as a benchmark, using which, all the dimensions and specifications of the catheter were replicated. The specifications available in the datasheet of the catheter were just the outer diameter of the catheter and the internal diameter of the catheter which was 1.66667mm and 1.19mm respectively. Other than that, no specifications like mesh diameter, mesh wire diameter, the pitch of the mesh, etc. were available. So to find out all these things, certain experimentations were performed upon the catheter.

The first experiment performed was aimed at determining the size, orientation, and dimension of the catheter mesh. The first step of this experiment was to strip the catheter polymer material from the mesh, such that the exposed mesh will be used for taking the measurement later. Many attempts were made to separate the mesh from the catheter material using techniques like cutting, scrubbing, abrasion, etc. but none of them were successful. So another technique was used, in which with the help of a flame, the catheter was burned. As the material covering the mesh was a polymer and had a very low melting point as compared to the mesh which was composed of stainless steel, melted away, giving us a perfectly stable and undeformed catheter mesh. The first observations of the mesh of a 5F catheter included that there were 16 strands of thin stainless steel wire intertwined with each other in a pair of two. So overall there were 8 pairs of stainless steel wire in which half of the wires were having a clockwise spiral and the other half had a counter-clockwise spiral pattern.

Upon learning all the things mentioned above, a second experiment was conducted to determine the dimension of a single strand of the catheter mesh. For that, all the 16 strands of the catheter mesh were separated individually. After separation, randomly 3

strands of the catheter mesh were selected and their dimension was measured with the help of a highly precise screw gauge. As per the procedure, all three strands were measured individually with the measurements being recorded at three different locations for each strand. Each strand was given a name as “Sample no. 1”, “Sample no. 2”, “Sample no. 3”, respectively. And the three cross-section locations were labeled as “Cross-section – a”, “Cross-section – b”, “Cross-section – c”, respectively. The observations are represented in table 4.1.

Sample no.	Cross Section	MSR (mm)	CSR (mm)	MSR+ (CSR*L.C.)	Average (mm)
1	1a	0	4	0.04	0.043
	1b	0	5	0.05	
	1c	0	4	0.04	
2	2a	0	4	0.04	0.04
	2b	0	4	0.04	
	2c	0	4	0.04	
3	3a	0	5	0.05	0.043
	3b	0	4	0.04	
	3c	0	4	0.04	
				Average	0.042

Table 4.1: Screw gauge readings of catheter strand

$$\text{Least count of Screw Gauge (LC)} = \frac{\text{pitch of the screw gauge}}{\text{total no. of divisions on circular scale}} = \frac{1}{100} = 0.01$$

From this experimentation, it was observed that the diameter of a single strand of the catheter mesh was about 0.042mm. As an addition to this, another experiment was conducted to determine the dimension of a single strand of the catheter mesh. For this experiment. A digital microscope with an attached micrometer scale was used to optically analyze the strand. Each segment on the scale depicted a distance of 10 microns or 0.01mm. The observation via the digital microscope is depicted in fig 4.11. a digital microscope is a type of microscope that can be found without an eyepiece attached to it. It directly converts the observed magnified specimen into a digital image, which can be used for further processing as per the need.

Fig 4.11: Observation through the digital microscope.

There were several errors present in this experiment primarily due to the non-straightening nature of the mesh strand and the shadowing error associated with an optical measurement device. From this output, it was assessed that the diameter of the strand was not more than 0.05mm. And by taking into consideration a magnitude of 15% shadow error, it was safe to assume that the diameter of the mesh strand was about 0.0425 mm. Therefore from analyzing the results from both the experiment, it was finalized that the mesh strand diameter after rounding off was to be considered as 0.04mm for the sake of designing and replicating the stainless steel reinforcement mesh present inside the catheter.

After evaluating the features and dimensions of a single strand, it was also important to find out the specifications and dimensions of the overall mesh which resides coaxially inside the catheter sheath, which primarily included finding out the diameter of the mesh. For that, a third experiment was conducted to determine the exact shape and dimension of the overall catheter mesh. Therefore, as mentioned in experiment 1, a screw gauge was used. A similar procedure was followed for measuring and determining the effective diameter of the mesh of the catheter as mentioned in experiment 1. Three separate samples were taken for the mesh and each sample was measured three times at three different locations on the sample. Table 4.2 below shows the cumulative data recorded for the dimension of the mesh of the catheter during the performance of the experiment.

$$\text{Least count of Screw Gauge (LC)} = \frac{\text{pitch of the screw gauge}}{\text{total no. of divisions on circular scale}} = \frac{1}{100} = 0.01$$

Sample no.	Cross Section	MSR (mm)	CSR (mm)	MSR+ (CSR*L.C.)	Average (mm)
1	1a	1	47	1.47	1.473
	1b	1	47	1.47	
	1c	1	46	1.46	
2	2a	1	46	1.46	1.453
	2b	1	45	1.45	
	2c	1	45	1.45	
3	3a	1	46	1.46	1.463
	3b	1	47	1.47	
	3c	1	46	1.46	
				Average	1.463

Table 4.2: screw gauge reading for catheter mesh

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Section plane diameter} &= \text{average mesh diameter} - 2 * \text{Radius of Mesh strand} \\ &= 1.463 - 0.04 \\ &= 1.423 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

From the dimensional data available from the datasheet and the experiments performed on the catheter, it can be observed that:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Catheter OD} &= 1.66 \text{ mm} \\ \text{Catheter ID} &= 1.19 \text{ mm} \\ \text{Centre plane diameter} &= (\text{OD} + \text{ID}) / 2 \\ &= (1.66 + 1.19) / 2 = 1.425 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

From the results above it can be concluded that the dimensional measurements obtained mathematically and the results obtained through experimentation are approximately the same. Hence it can be said that the dimensions obtained experimentally are correct and applicable for replication of Catheter design virtually.

4.2.2 Computer-Aided Design and Modelling:

After acquiring dimensional data from the above-mentioned experimentations, the catheter was recreated in the virtual domain using computer-aided design software. Initially, the software primarily used for designing the mesh, and the catheter was Dassault CATIA V5. The catheter was to be designed in two parts, first the wire mesh of the catheter and second, the cylindrical tubular structure covering the mesh. So firstly, an attempt was made to create the virtual replica of the catheter mesh in the CATIA V5 environment. As per the structural and dimensional data gathered through the experiment, it was revealed that the mesh is having sinusoidal shaped strands following a spiral pattern. Therefore, it meant that in the software firstly we had to create a sinusoidal strand for the mesh and then reform that stand in a spiral pattern. This meant giving two distinct attributes to a single strand and then combining all 16 strands to make a complete mesh. As the CATIA V5 is older software, there is no simple way to just bend a solid component in a spiral shape. Therefore, the design of the catheter for the sake of analysis was later performed over a different CAD software called SOLIDWORKS. SOLIDWORKS being a newer software compared to CATIAV5 has a lot more features and an easy to use interface. For creating the mesh, firstly a grid of sinusoidal waves was drawn by placing 2 sinusoidal waves perpendicular to each other having a phase difference of 90° . Using that sinusoidal grid lines as a spline, a tube of required dimension was extruded over it. This procedure was repeated for all the 16 sinusoidal waves which were drawn as depicted in fig 4.12.

Fig 4.12: The sinusoidal grid of strands

When the grid was cut such that it matches the required dimensions. Then by using the “Flex” command. Using this command, we were able to bend the mesh about itself such that when it is completely folded for 360°, it must form a cylindrical structure (fig 4.13). With this, the virtual recreation of the mesh was complete as shown in fig 4.14 and for the outer catheter sheath, a simple hollow cylindrical structure was created using the specified dimensions as observed during experimentation (fig 4.15).

Fig 4.13: Folding the strand grid using “Flex” feature

Fig 4.14: CAD model of Catheter mesh

Using these two individual virtual models, an assembly was created such that these both components be placed coaxially hence completely recreating the catheter virtually in SOLIDWORKS as shown in fig 4.16. For the sake of Finite Element Analysis (FEA), there was an additional step in the assembly that was taken so that the model can be analyzed properly. In this step, after placing the mesh and the catheter shell coaxially, the mesh went completely inside the shell and created an ambiguity as two distinct materials were present as a single point. Therefore, it was necessary to make space for the mesh inside the catheter shell such that no interference must take place. Therefore, another command “Cavity” such that a proper gap was created between the mesh and the shell so that no interference takes place. After this, the model was converted into IGES format such that it can be used by analysis software.

Fig 4.15: catheter exterior sheath

Fig 4.16: catheter mesh and sheath assembly

4.2.3 Static Analysis of Catheter:

After recreating the catheter in a virtual domain using CAD software, the model was used to analyze the effects of a static force applied to the catheter. This was done with the help of Finite Element Method (FEM). Studying a model is often referred to as Finite Element Analysis (FEA). Finite Element Analysis is a numerical method for solving engineering and mathematical models. To solve a problem, the model is subdivided into smaller, similar parts called “finite elements”. This is achieved by the construction of a mesh of an object. These finite elements are represented by a set of element equations individually and then their respective equations are assembled to get the resultant equation of the larger section which is eventually solved to get the final results.

Material	Mechanical Properties						
	Density (Kg/m ³)	Tensile yield strength (Mpa)	Compressive yield strength (Mpa)	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Coefficient of Friction	Thermal Conductivity (W/m-K)	Melting Point (°C)
Polyethylene terephthalate (DACRON)	1280	64.2	45.2	3.12	0.228	0.202	246
Nylon 12	1350	43	67.6	4.37	0.312	3.01	178
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR)	1200	13.7	10.2	0.780	0.268	-	148
High Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	954	26.1	12.6	0.976	0.3	0.396	131
Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC)	1300	14	8.4	2.16	0.296	-	174
Poly tetra fluoro ethylene (PTFE) (TEFLON)	2150	25	7	0.410	0.0631	0.263	323
Stainless Steel	8000	215	272	197	0.5	16.2	1430

Table 4.3: Material properties of applied materials.

For the sake of analyzing the catheter under certain force conditions firstly, some materials were applied to the catheter assembly. As the catheter sheath and the catheter mesh are having two distinct materials, therefore the catheter mesh was applied with Stainless Steel and the sheath was applied with the materials like Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) also commonly known as “Dacron”, Nylon-12, Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR), High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE), Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) and Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) which is commonly called “Teflon”. The material properties[61] of aforesaid materials are mentioned in table 4.3.

These materials were applied separately each time and respective results were obtained for each polymer material applied upon the catheter sheath. After the application of the materials, the model was “meshed” according to the procedure of Finite element analysis. As the smallest dimension in the entire model is 0.04mm, i.e. the diameter of the catheter mesh strand, the ‘meshing element’ dimension was chosen to be 0.02mm as to get a good two-layer mesh in the catheter strand. The catheter after meshing is depicted in fig 4.17.

Fig 4.17: Catheter model after meshing for FEA

After meshing, the next step was to assign parameters, upon which the model was to be analyzed. As per the Finite Element Analysis procedure, fixed support was applied to the base of the catheter, and a force was applied from the diametrically opposite side to the support. An incrementally increasing force from zero newtons to ten newtons with a step of 0.5 newtons was applied onto the model of the catheter. Table 4.4 depicts the applied force concerning steps.

Force (N)	0	0.5	1	1.5	2	2.5	3	3.5	4	4.5	5	5.5	6	6.5	7	7.5	8	8.5	9	9.5	10
Step	0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20

Table 4.4: Stepwise applied force

The parameters for which the analysis was performed included the following:

- a) **Maximum deformation:** change in the shape of a body caused by the application of a force. Deformation is proportional to the stress within the elastic limit of the material.
- b) **Von-Mises Stress:** It is defined as the uniaxial tensile stress that would create the same distortion energy as is created by actual combined applied stress. It is often used in determining the yielding of isotropic and ductile material subjected to complex loading conditions.
- c) **Elastic strain:** It is defined as the limit of the value of strain up to which the object will regain its original shape once the applied force is removed.

The results of the FEM analysis are as displayed below:

Force (N)	Deformation (μm)					
	PTFE Teflon	NYLON 12	PET Dacron	TPUR	HDPE	PVC
0.5	5.304	0.532	0.72	2.85	2.3	1.06
1	10.608	1.064	1.45	5.7	4.61	2.11
1.5	15.912	1.596	2.17	8.55	6.91	3.17
2	21.215	2.128	2.9	11.4	9.22	4.23
2.5	26.519	2.661	3.63	14.25	11.53	5.29
3	31.823	3.193	4.35	17.1	13.83	6.35
3.5	37.127	3.725	5.08	19.95	16.14	7.41
4	42.431	4.257	5.8	22.8	18.45	8.47
4.5	47.735	4.789	6.59	25.65	20.75	9.53
5	53.038	5.3222	7.26	28.5	23.06	10.59
5.5	58.342	5.854	7.98	31.35	25.37	11.65
6	63.646	6.386	8.71	34.2	27.67	12.71
6.5	68.95	6.918	9.43	37.06	29.98	13.77
7	74.254	7.451	10.164	39.91	32.29	14.83
7.5	79.558	7.983	10.89	42.76	34.59	15.89
8	84.862	8.515	11.61	45.61	36.9	16.95
8.5	90.165	9.047	12.34	48.46	39.21	18.01
9	95.469	9.579	13.06	51.31	41.51	19.67
9.5	100.77	10.112	13.79	54.16	43.82	20.13
10	106.08	10.644	14.52	57.01	46.13	21.19

Table 4.5: The comparative result of force v/s deformation for different materials

Fig 4.18: Graph of force v/s deformation for different materials.

Force (N)	Max Von-Mises Stress (Mpa)					
	PTFE	NYLON 12	PET Dacron	TPUR	HDPE	PVC
0.5	41.813	8.83	9.76	25.64	20.98	11.96
1	83.617	17.65	19.5	51.28	41.94	23.91
1.5	125.43	26.48	29.26	76.92	62.92	35.87
2	167.23	35.31	39.01	102.57	83.89	47.82
2.5	209.04	44.14	48.77	128.21	104.87	59.78
3	250.85	52.97	58.52	153.85	125.84	71.74
3.5	292.66	61.8	68.28	179.49	146.82	83.69
4	334.47	70.63	78.03	205.13	167.79	95.65
4.5	376.28	79.46	87.78	230.77	188.76	107.61
5	418.08	88.28	97.54	256.42	209.74	119.57
5.5	459.89	97.11	107.3	282.06	230.71	131.53
6	501.7	105.95	117.05	307.7	251.68	143.48
6.5	543.51	114.78	126.81	333.34	272.66	155.44
7	585.32	123.6	136.56	358.9	293.63	167.4
7.5	627.13	132.43	146.31	384.6	314.61	179.35
8	668.94	141.26	156.07	410.27	335.58	191.31
8.5	710.74	150.09	165.82	435.91	356.55	203.27
9	752.55	158.92	175.58	461.55	377.53	215.22
9.5	794.36	167.75	185.33	487.19	398.5	227.18
10	836.17	176.58	195.08	512.83	419.47	239.14

Table 4.6: The comparative result of force v/s Max Von-Mises Stress for different materials

Fig 4.19: Graph of force v/s Max Von-Mises Stress for different materials

Force (N)	Max Elastic Strain (mm/mm)					
	PTFE	NYLON 12	PET Dacron	TPUR	HDPE	PVC
0.5	8.97	0.9	1.34	5.105	4.09	1.83
1	17.94	1.78	2.64	10.225	8	3.64
1.5	26.91	2.68	3.98	15.33	12.09	5.47
2	35.88	3.57	5.31	20.45	16.01	7.29
2.5	44.85	4.47	6.64	25.56	20.01	9.12
3	53.82	5.36	7.94	30.67	24.01	10.94
3.5	62.79	6.25	9.29	35.78	28.02	12.77
4	71.76	7.15	10.62	40.9	32.02	14.59
4.5	80.73	8.04	11.95	46.01	36.02	16.421
5	89.7	8.94	13.28	51.12	40.03	18.24
5.5	98.67	9.83	14.61	56.23	44.03	20.07
6	107.64	10.73	15.93	61.35	48.03	21.89
6.5	116.61	11.6625	17.26	66.46	52.04	23.71
7	125.58	12.519	18.59	71.57	56.04	25.54
7.5	134.55	13.414	19.92	76.68	60.04	27.36
8	143.55	14.308	21.25	81.8	64.04	29.19
8.5	152.49	15.202	22.58	86.91	68.05	31.01
9	161.46	16.096	23.9	92.02	72.05	32.84
9.5	170.43	16.99	25.23	97.14	76.05	34.66
10	179.4	17.885	26.56	102.25	80.06	36.49

Table 4.7: The comparative result of force v/s Max Elastic strain for different materials

Fig 4.20: Graph of force v/s Max Elastic strain for different materials

From the above results, it was clear that under a similar load, the model of a catheter made of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) material endured the maximum deformation whereas the model of a catheter made up of NYLON-12 material experienced the least deformation. The same trend was observed in the Equivalent Von-Mises stress as well as Equivalent elastic strain. The material-wise progression for all the results can be wrapped up as: PTFE > TPUR > HDPE > PVC > PET > NYLON 12.

Therefore, from the results as shown in following figures, it can be concluded that from the perspective of operational deformation in the developed robotic catheterization system, a catheter made up of NYLON- 12 material will be the most effective, efficient and will be preferred over catheters made of different materials for pressure-related medical procedures like oxygen saturation monitoring, diagnostically dye injecting procedures, etc. the catheters made up of Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) and High-Density Polyethylene (HDPE) can also be used for low risk or medium risk applications. Depicted below in fig 4.21, are the visual results of deformation obtained by finite element analysis. Results for Von-Mises stress and Elastic strain are mentioned in the Appendix.

Fig 4.21: FEA deformation results

4.3 Force and Torque modelling for the roller mechanism

From the design of the system, it can be seen that the force eventually responsible for imparting the motion on the catheter in front axial drive as well as rear rotational drive is the force provided by the spring incorporated into the design of the respective drive systems. Therefore, by formulating some mathematical derivation, we established a relationship between the force provided by the spring in the axial drive as well as rotational drive and the driving torque provided by the actuating motors to, the physical parameters of the other components of the axial drive system as well as the components of the rotational drive system.

The derivation for the force relationship for the axial drive and rotational drive is depicted in the subsequent sections respectively.

4.3.1 Force equation for front assembly

Fig 4.22: Force diagram for the front axial drive

Total applied force $F_a = \frac{F_p}{FoS}$ (1)

where, F_p is the maximum permissible force and FoS is the factor of safety

Also, $F_a = F_{sf} - \text{friction force}$, where F_{sf} being the force applied by the front spring.

As the applicable frictional force equals to “ $\mu_s m_f g$ ”

Therefore, $F_{sf} = F_a + \mu_s m_f g$ (2)

Where ‘ μ_s ’ is the coefficient of friction for the slider, ‘ m_f ’ being the mass of the front slider and ‘ g ’ being acceleration due to gravity.

As there are 2 springs in parallel,

$F_{sf} = 2 F_{kf}$, which implies, $F_{kf} = \frac{F_{sf}}{2}$,

where F_{kf} is the force applied by the spring in front axial drive mechanism, and by using equation (2) we get,

$$F_{kf} = \frac{F_a + \mu_s m_f g}{2}$$

therefore, by substituting $F_a = \frac{F_p}{FoS}$ from equation (1) we get

$$F_{kf} = \frac{F_p / FoS + (\mu_s \cdot m_f \cdot g)}{2} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

4.3.2 Torque equation for front assembly

Frictional force on catheter $F_{cf} = \mu_c N_f$

Where ‘ μ_c ’ being the coefficient of friction for the catheter and ‘ N_f ’ being the normal force responsible for generating friction.

$$\text{Therefore, } F_{cf} = \mu_c \frac{F_{sf}}{2} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where, $N_f = \frac{F_{sf}}{2}$ due to the design considerations.

The force provided by the motor (F_{mf}) must be greater than the frictional force, Therefore, $F_{mf} = 2F_{cf}$, where being the Frictional force on catheter as mentioned before.

As the gear ratio is 1:1, torque provided by the motor $\tau_f = F_{mf} \frac{d}{2}$, where ‘ d ’ being the diameter of the rollers, which implies that, $F_{mf} = \frac{2\tau_f}{d}$

Therefore, $\frac{2\tau_f}{d} = 2F_{cf}$, thus by rearranging the terms and using equation (4), we obtain,

$$\tau_f = F_{cf} \cdot d = \mu_c \frac{F_{sf}}{2} d, \dots\dots\dots(5)$$

and by using equation (1) and equation (2) in equation (5) we get

$$\tau_f = \mu_c \left[\frac{F_p}{F_{OS}} + \mu_s m_f g \right] \frac{d}{2} \dots\dots\dots(6)$$

4.3.3 Torque equation for rear assembly

Fig 4.23: Force diagram for rear rotational drive

Force applied by the spring in rear assembly $F_{sr} = F_a + \mu_s m_r g \dots\dots\dots(7)$

Where ‘ F_a ’ being the total applied force, ‘ μ_s ’ is the coefficient of friction for the slider, ‘ m_r ’ being the mass of the front slider and ‘ g ’ being acceleration due to gravity.

As there are 2 springs in parallel,

$$F_{sr} = 2 F_{kr}$$

where F_{kr} is the force applied by the single spring in the rear rotational drive mechanism, and by rearranging terms and using equation (7) we get,

$$F_{kr} = \frac{F_a + \mu_s m_r g}{2}$$

therefore, by substituting $F_a = \frac{F_p}{F_{oS}}$ from equation (1) we get

$$F_{kr} = \frac{F_p/F_{oS} + (\mu_s.m_r.g)}{2} \dots\dots\dots(8)$$

The friction force between the catheter and roller $F_{cr} = \mu_c.N_r$

Where ‘ μ_c ’ being the coefficient of friction for the catheter and ‘ N_r ’ being the normal force responsible for generating friction.

Therefore, substituting $N_r = \frac{F_{sr}}{4}$ and using equation (7) we get,

$$F_{cr} = \frac{\mu_c [F_a + \mu_s m_r g]}{4} \dots\dots\dots(9)$$

Therefore frictional torque provided by motor $\tau_r = F_{cr} d_c$, where ‘ d_c ’ is the diameter of the catheter. By using equation (1) and equation (9) we get,

$$\tau_r = \mu_c \left[\frac{F_p}{F_{oS}} + \mu_s m_r g \right] \frac{d_c}{4} \dots\dots\dots(10)$$

From the experimentation and analysis done on the catheter, we got several results respective to different catheter materials. In the context of structural deformation, maximum deformation was observed in catheter made up of PTFE and minimum deformation was observed in catheter made up of NYLON 12. From the graph of force v/s deformation (fig:4.19) we derived the linear equation as following:

- For PTFE: $Y = 10.608 X + 0.00003$
- For NYLON 12 : $Y = 1.0644 X - 0.0004$

Therefore, considering the maximum permissible deformation of 50 μ m, the force required for such deformation is as follows:

- For PTFE ($F_{p, PTFE}$): 4.7134 N
- For NYLON 12 ($F_{p, NYLON 12}$): 46.975 N

Therefore, spring force for both the materials was calculated considering the following:

Max. permissible force	F_p (N)
Factor of safety (FoS)	1.5
Coefficient of friction for slider (μ_s)	0.45
Material for slider in axial drive and rotational drive	Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS)
Mass of slider of axial drive (m_f)	33×10^{-3} Kg
Mass of slider of rotational drive (m_r)	15.57×10^{-3} Kg
Accelaration due to gravity (g)	9.81 m/s ²

Table 4.8: Considerations for spring force calculations

therefore by using the formula for spring force (front) F_k and spring force (rear) F_{kr} , by using equation (3) and (8) we get,

$$F_{kf, PTFE} = 1.6439 \text{ N}, F_{kr, PTFE} = 1.6055 \text{ N} \text{ and,}$$

$$F_{kf, NYLON 12} = 15.7311 \text{ N}, F_{kr, NYLON 12} = 15.6927 \text{ N}$$

Therefore, from these results, it can be observed that, for the proper working of the front axial drive system and rear rotational drive system, springs providing a force in between this range has to be incorporated in the system for using catheters of different materials.

4.4 Spring Selection

Spring is an elastic device that stores mechanical energy. In a conventional spring, it exerts a force when it is stretched or compressed from its natural resting position on the opposite side proportional to change in its length. For various applications, several different types of springs are available such as:

- According to the load applied: Tension spring, compression spring[62], torsion spring, constant support spring, variable resistance spring, variable stiffness spring.

- According to shape: helical spring, leaf spring, Belleville disc, conical spring[63], circular C shape spring[64][65][66], flexure spring [67]

The conventional springs are made of particularly of spring steel material. This steel is a low manganese medium carbon alloy steel which is having a very high yield strength. These springs are generally used for high load scenarios[68]. But for low load scenarios like in this system, several innovative designs of springs are required. As the load-bearing capacity of the spring is dependent on the material properties such as ultimate tensile strength (S_{ut}) and the shear modulus (G) of the material, therefore materials having high strength and shear modulus cannot be used for low load conditions. Therefore, some unconventional materials[69] are used to meet such requirements, which include Brass, Polyetherimide (PEI) resin, silicon, polysorb, fiber glass[70], carbon fiber, rubber[71], etc. There are also certain unconventional designs such as Wave spiral springs which have flat wires used in wave pattern wounded in spiral form. These are used in the applications requiring tight load deflection in the space-critical environment.

Springs are made of polymer resins such as Polyetherimide (PEI) because the ultimate tensile strength of the polymer material is very low as compared to conventional metals. These polymers are able to provide good structural integrity under loading conditions and they do not require large forces to cause deformation. The spring constant “ k ” (N/m) of springs made up of such materials is very low, perfectly suitable for small load applications[72]. Another advantage of using such polymer materials instead of regular metals for making springs of low load conditions is that, if the spring is made up of metal, the effective diameter of the spring wire will be very thin, sometimes even in microns(μm) and the spring length and total deflection will also be very small[73]. Therefore, those springs being very small and fragile, cannot be used in systems where the spring is required larger in its dimensions but for a low level of load[74]. Also working with a thin wire spring is very complicated as it is prone to fatigue as well as a failure even with slightest disarrangement.

Springs made of polysorb and similar materials are generally used for making Belleville disc. They are mainly used for shock-absorbing applications where low load and small dimensional conditions are present. Silicon is generally used for making bushes that are used for structural stability and jerk resistance situations. Brass is an alloy metal that

has high ductility as compared to general spring steel[75], therefore it can be drawn into wires having very small diameters, which is not possible in the case of steel as it is a bit brittle as compared to brass. Also, the ultimate tensile strength (S_{ut}) of Brass is very low as compared to its conventional counterpart, therefore it is possible to make a spring out of brass having low spring constant “ k ” and bigger dimensional features.

This chapter accommodates the accounts of experiments and analyses performed on the catheter. To analyze the catheter using FEM analysis, a 3D CAD model was created using SOLIDWORKS. Catheter mesh and sheath were separately created and assembled together. FEM analysis was done using ANSYS software. Several materials were applied to the catheter model such as PTFE, Nylon-12, PET, TPUR, PVC, HDPE, etc. several parameters such as deformation, stress, elastic strain experienced by the catheter were analyzed and compared. It was observed that PTFE experienced maximum deformation and Nylon-12 experienced the least deformation under similar loading conditions. Using these results, a relationship between force provided by the spring and other physical parameters of the drive system was established and a brief review of springs was discussed.

CHAPTER 5: RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After reviewing all the literature and the studies conducted around catheterization and robot-assisted cardiac catheterization it was observed that the physician performing the cardiac catheterization procedure manually absorbs a very high amount of radiation dosage emitted from the fluoroscope. Even after using protective clothing such as lead aprons and face shields, some body parts such as wrists, neck, thyroid region, and eyes do absorb the radiation and the chances of occurrence of physiological complications in these regions are quite high. With the advancement in technology, the machine is getting better and safer, but the risk of absorbing leaked radiation is still very high. The study also showed that the existing mortality rate and the rate of complication post-procedure performed manually can be severely brought down by using robotic cardiac catheterization systems. It was also observed that the procedures performed using robotic cardiac catheterization systems were safer, precise and took a very less amount of procedural time as compared to the manual procedure and the amount of radiation absorbed by the operating physician during the procedure was also minuscule when using the robotic system as compared to manual procedures. While reviewing the work done by researchers in the past on designing and development of a robotic system for cardiac catheterization, it was observed that it was more feasible to use a roller to impart linear motion to the catheter and for rotation, rotating the whole assembly was preferred. There were also instances which indicated that for smoother travel and precise turning of the catheter, the pulley belt mechanism was more beneficial as compared to the geared mechanism as it may create backlash which might become the cause of traveling inaccuracy.

5.1 Mechanism for Catheter Motion

The design of a driving mechanism for the catheter in the robotic cardiac catheterization system went through an evolutionary phase that started with a single drive capable of providing both linear and rotational motion to the catheter using a reverse lead screw mechanism powered only by a combination of linear actuators. This drive has a severe disadvantage as it had imparted dimensional limitations on the catheter. The catheter was able to move only a certain distance and rotate only till certain angles. To improve these conditions, the second drive mechanism was developed which was based on a geared mechanism. This drive gave an unlimited turning angle to the catheter but was

still imparting limitations on linear travel length. Therefore to overcome all these limitations, two separate drive systems for axial motion and rotational motion were conceptualized.

Fig 5.1: CAD model of Robotic cardiac catheterization system

These both drive mechanisms were roller based and can be electronically actuated using motors. After improving these two drive mechanisms independently the full-fledged robotic catheterization system was developed.

The robotic system assembly finally comprised of a support base which also worked as actuator housing, an axial drive with a double roller configuration to provide smoother and precise linear travel to the catheter and a smaller, light in weight rotational drive which rotated along the longitudinal axis of the catheter providing accurate turning angles to the catheter.

5.2 Catheter design and Modeling

To analyze the performance of the catheter under certain loading conditions, a virtual model of the catheter was created using computer-aided design. Both the parts of the catheter which were an inner mesh and an outer sheath were created separately and then assembled together to form a perfect virtual model. This model was then used to observe the results of static structural analysis on the catheter.

Fig 5.2: CAD model of Catheter mesh

The static structural analysis performed on the catheter has shown us that how would the catheter behave when it experiences a certain amount of loading conditions. By applying a varying force of zero newtons to ten newtons over one side of the catheter while the diametrically opposite side of the catheter was fixed. By performing the analysis on a wide range of material, it was observed that different materials behaved differently. The system was analyzed for three parameters which included maximum deformation, maximum Von-Mises stress, and maximum elastic strain. From the results, it was concluded that the catheter made of Polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) had the highest deformation and Nylon-12 had the least of deformation under similar loading conditions. And by comparing the results of all the materials, a sequence of PTFE > TPUR > HDPE > PVC > PET > NYLON 12 can be observed. The significance of analyzing the deformation is that it signifies as how much dimensional change will occur under such loading conditions.

As these catheters are used in medical procedures working with dyes, blood, and other fluids, the principle of operation is sometimes the pressure of the fluid column inside the catheter. The best example of this is the procedure of measuring oxygen saturation inside a human heart chamber. As part of the process, the blood pressure inside the chamber of the heart is also measured. That blood pressure is measured by sensing the pressure of the blood inside the catheter. Some deformation in the shape of the catheter will change the dimension of the internal diameter which in turn will give inaccurate blood pressure readings, leading to unfavorable consequences.

Fig 5.3: Forces in the robotic assembly

The robotic system designed for operating and manipulating the catheter has a set of springs as the source for the application of force on the catheter. This analysis also helps to determine what type or what kind of spring to be used such that deformation of the catheter can be avoided and the system stays perfectly operational.

As mentioned before, the operational parameters of the robotic catheterization system are heavily dependent on the force provided by the spring. The spring is a source component for the availability of frictional force for the catheter. The analysis performed over the catheter gave the maximum allowable force to be applied to the catheter for operation without deformation. The derivation of force equations helped in analyzing the force required to be applied by the spring. It can also be said that the force equations helped us determining the spring constant of the spring required for the operating procedure. With the help of this information, the designing of a specialized spring for this robotic system can be done.

This data will help in the selection of material for the spring as well as the shape and dimensions of the spring element (spring wire). As the requirement of the force applied by the spring is very low, this data can be used for developing a specialized polymer compound only to be used as material for this spring.

5.3 Discussion

The robotic catheterization system developed has so many positives associated with it. First and foremost it achieves its primary objective of separating catheterization procedure performing physicians from the harmful radiation packed environment. It will be highly beneficial for the medical personnel as he will be guarded against all the ailments that come with this form of work which includes fatigue, lumbar spinal injuries radiation-related complications, etc. The robotic system is developed with replaceable parts for axial and rotational drives.

The parts which are in direct contact with the catheter are designed such that they can be replaced with a fresh component for a new procedure or can be sterilized separately. For maintaining the sterility of the system, it is not required to sterilize the whole robotic assembly. Using this system for cardiac catheterization will make the procedure more accurate, precise, and swift. Performing cardiac catheterization with a robotic system is less time-consuming. The time taken for performing the procedure manually takes around twice the time consumed by performing it robotically.

On the downside, the robotic system has no feedback mechanism during the operating procedure. While performing catheterization manually, the physician receives tactile feedback with a sense of touch.

As there are no sensors attached to the catheter and there is no provision of sensing feedback force in the drive system, any obstruction during the travel of the catheter can not be determined by the operating physician and he has to rely on visual support only. Having no tactile feedback can result in trauma to blood vessels, the formation of thrombosis, etc. also, as the main driving component for both axial as well as rotational drive is friction between rollers and the outer surface of the catheter.

As most catheters have a PTFE film placed on their outermost surface for smooth and frictionless travel inside the blood vessel, it often creates a chance of slippage during its interaction with the rollers. For avoiding this, a material of a higher coefficient of friction must be placed on the roller side to avoid this situation from occurring.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

6.1 Conclusion

In summary, it can be concluded that this thesis was aimed to design and develop a robotic system having two degrees of freedom to perform cardiac catheterization. The development of this robotic system was to protect medical professionals from the ill effects of harmful fluoroscopic radiation. This device will also help increase the accuracy and precision of the procedure along with reducing procedural time. This thesis is comprising of literature surveys done in order to gather information about the effects of radiation on medical personnel, comparison between manual and robotic catheterization, research done by other researchers all over the globe on robotic catheterization system, and accounts of clinical trials done to assess the robotic catheterization systems.

The thesis has a detailed account of the evolution of design for both forward axial drive as well as rear rotational drive. It describes the advancement of the idea to achieve the desirable drive system capable to be applied in the working environment. It included the design and development lead screw mechanism, geared mechanism, frictional slab mechanism, and double roller mechanism for the axial drive as well as the design of double set rotational drive and single set rotational drive.

The thesis also encompasses a detailed description of recreating a model of the catheter in the virtual domain using computer-aided design software like CATIA V5 and SOLIDWORKS. It includes the account of experimentation done to gather dimensional data necessary for creating a virtual CAD model with the help of micrometer screw gauges as well as digital microscopes and the procedure involved in actually creating the model detailing some important features and commands used in the SOLIDWORKS software. Designing of catheter parts included creating the catheter mesh and catheter sheath in the virtual environment.

A part of the thesis also includes the procedure and the results of the static structural analysis performed over the catheter model by the principles of the finite element method using simulation and analysis software ANSYS. The results showed that under the influence of certain loading conditions, the deformation, stress, and elastic strain experienced by the catheter for different materials such as PTFE, NYLON-12, PET Dacron, TPUR, HDPE, and PVC. The comparison of respective results reflected that the maximum stress, strain, and deformation was experienced in the following order PTFE > TPUR > HDPE > PVC > PET > NYLON-12 with PTFE experiencing highest and NYLON-12 experiencing the lowest values comparatively. After acquiring the statistical data from the analysis, some force equations were derived in order to associate the allowable amount of force on the catheter to the force required to be applied by the springs present on the drive systems. the application of numerical values to these equations will eventually help in setting the design parameters to manufacture the spring for this specific system.

In conclusion, the thesis covers all the accounts of designing and developing an indigenous robotic cardiac catheterization system and the parameters required to assess its feasibility and applicability for practical implementation.

6.2 Future Scope

In subsequent work, several points have a large scope of further research and development for refining and improving the working of the robotic cardiac catheterization system. The first point included the lack of tactile feedback from the catheter tip to the operating physician. in the current system, there is no provision to measure or predict the force experienced by the tip of the catheter while hitting the wall of the blood vessel. Development on this issue will help severely reducing the trauma experienced by the walls of the blood vessels and the complications associated with it.

Another scope of future work includes designing and manufacturing of a specialized spring, intended only to be used in the robotic cardiac catheterization system. The main area of research will be developing a composite polymer material for the spring which will be competent in fulfilling all the necessary requirements of material specifications. Research can also be done on creating novel alloys of different metals to achieve the desired material properties of low load applicable spring material.

With this robotic system destined to be used in medical applications, there is a tremendous scope of research to elevate the level of achievable sterility during procedure and post-procedure. As sterility is one of the major components of any medical procedure, so improvement in sterility standards of the system can be achieved by improving and fine-tuning the design of the drive components and/or adding external safety components to the system.

With all the points mentioned above, it is safe to say that this robotic cardiac catheterization system has a long way to go to achieve its envisioned status of practical application in hospitals and competing with commercially available counterparts worldwide.

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APPENDIX

I. FEM Analysis report for PTFE catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Wednesday, June 17, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

Contents

- Units
- Model (B4)
 - Geometry
 - Parts
 - Materials
 - Coordinate Systems
 - Connections
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 - Static Structural (B5)
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 - Solution (B6)
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- Material Data
 - PTFE
 - Stainless Steel

Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	<i>Geometry</i>	
State	Fully Defined	
Definition		
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS	
Type	Iges	
Length Unit	Millimeters	
Element Control	Program Controlled	
Display Style	Body Color	
Bounding Box		
Length X	5.2663e-003 m	
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m	
Properties		
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³	
Mass	2.2267e-005 kg	
Scale Factor Value	1.	
Statistics		
Bodies	33	
Active Bodies	33	
Nodes	1298778	
Elements	572198	
Mesh Metric	None	
Update Options		
Assign Default Material	No	
Basic Geometry Options		

Solid Bodies	Yes
Surface Bodies	Yes
Line Bodies	No
Parameters	Independent
Parameter Key	ANS;DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext</i> 12	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [2]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [3]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [4]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [5]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [6]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [7]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [8]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [9]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [10]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	PTFE	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	2.1144e-005 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	5.1261e-011 kg·m ²	3.364e-015 kg·m ²	1.0846e-014 kg·m ²	8.036e-015 kg·m ²	1.383e-013 kg·m ²	3.9734e-014 kg·m ²	9.1268e-018 kg·m ²	3.9899e-015 kg·m ²	2.1764e-014 kg·m ²	6.852e-014 kg·m ²	4.5184e-016 kg·m ²
	5.1357e-	3.2839e-	1.0427e-	6.0994e-	1.2615e-	4.3132e-	4.3506e-	4.3183e-	1.2351e-	6.2174e-	1.0892e-

Moment of Inertia Ip2	011 kg·m ²	015 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²	013 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²	016 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²	013 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²	014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	1.4295e-011 kg·m ²	8.5963e-017 kg·m ²	4.5001e-016 kg·m ²	6.723e-014 kg·m ²	2.2259e-014 kg·m ²	3.9837e-015 kg·m ²	4.424e-016 kg·m ²	3.978e-014 kg·m ²	1.3538e-013 kg·m ²	8.1706e-015 kg·m ²	1.0471e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [11]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [12]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [13]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [14]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [15]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [16]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [17]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [18]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [19]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [20]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [21]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m ³	6.8831e-012 m ³	7.003e-012 m ³	2.0829e-012 m ³	4.0944e-012 m ³	1.036e-012 m ³	4.0971e-012 m ³	7.8003e-012 m ³	4.9869e-012 m ³	2.0831e-012 m ³	3.1329e-012 m ³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg·m ²	1.4058e-014 kg·m ²	1.4313e-014 kg·m ²	8.6022e-017 kg·m ²	2.3766e-014 kg·m ²	9.1109e-018 kg·m ²	2.374e-014 kg·m ²	2.1578e-014 kg·m ²	3.9248e-015 kg·m ²	8.6031e-017 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg·m ²	8.8508e-014 kg·m ²	9.0265e-014 kg·m ²	3.2869e-015 kg·m ²	1.5526e-015 kg·m ²	4.3474e-016 kg·m ²	1.5509e-015 kg·m ²	1.2304e-013 kg·m ²	4.2541e-014 kg·m ²	3.2872e-015 kg·m ²	1.0872e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg·m ²	9.799e-014 kg·m ²	9.9888e-014 kg·m ²	3.3668e-015 kg·m ²	2.2364e-014 kg·m ²	4.4206e-016 kg·m ²	2.2339e-014 kg·m ²	1.3482e-013 kg·m ²	3.9182e-014 kg·m ²	3.3671e-015 kg·m ²	1.0452e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

	<i>WFH mesh</i>										
--	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	-----------------

Object Name	folded00 [22]	folded00 [23]	folded00 [24]	folded00 [25]	folded00 [26]	folded00 [27]	folded00 [28]	folded00 [29]	folded00 [30]	folded00 [31]	folded00 [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-004 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-014 kg·m ²	1.367e-013 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-016 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-014 kg·m ²	1.2475e-013 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-016 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	Materials
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	2
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	Global Coordinate System
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Type	Cartesian
Coordinate System ID	0.

Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces		
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										

Behavior	Program Controlled
Trim Contact	Program Controlled
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m
Suppressed	No
Advanced	
Formulation	Program Controlled
Small Sliding	Program Controlled
Detection Method	Program Controlled
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										

Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces		5 Faces			4 Faces		1 Face
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										WFH mesh folded00
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										

Contact	1 Face										
Target	1 Face										
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			
Detection Method	Program Controlled			
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled			

Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	<i>Mesh</i>
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m
Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m
Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	<i>Static Structural (B5)</i>
State	Solved
Definition	
Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural
Solver Target	Mechanical APDL

Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	<i>Analysis Settings</i>	
State	Fully Defined	
Step Controls		
Number Of Steps	20.	
Current Step Number	1.	
Step End Time	1. s	
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled	
Solver Controls		
Solver Type	Program Controlled	
Weak Springs	Off	
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled	
Large Deflection	Off	
Inertia Relief	Off	
Rotordynamics Controls		
Coriolis Effect	Off	
Restart Controls		
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled	
Retain Files After Full Solve	No	
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled	
Nonlinear Controls		
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled	
Force Convergence	Program Controlled	
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled	
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled	
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled	
Line Search	Program Controlled	
Stabilization	Program Controlled	
Output Controls		
Stress	Yes	
Surface Stress	No	
Back Stress	No	
Strain	Yes	
Contact Data	Yes	
Nonlinear Data	No	
Nodal Forces	No	
Contact Miscellaneous	No	
General Miscellaneous	No	
Store Results At	All Time Points	
Result File Compression	Program Controlled	
Analysis Data Management		
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0 \SYS\MECH\	
Future Analysis	None	
Scratch Solver Files Directory		
Save MAPDL db	No	
Contact Summary	Program Controlled	
Delete Unneeded Files	Yes	
Nonlinear Solution	No	
Solver Units	Active System	
Solver Unit System	mks	

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s
4	4. s
5	5. s
6	6. s

7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	Fixed Support	Force
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By		Vector
Magnitude		Tabular Data
Direction		Defined
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable		Time

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.
4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.
6	6.	3.5

7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	<i>Solution (B6)</i>
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	2 h 51 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.6514 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.382 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		
Identifier			
Suppressed	No		
Results			

Minimum	0. m	0.21227 Pa	6.406e-012 m/m
Maximum	1.0608e-004 m	8.3617e+008 Pa	0.1794 m/m
Average	3.5681e-005 m	5.1865e+007 Pa	8.0156e-003 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[16]	
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[10]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	2.2475e-002 Pa	6.7623e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	0.21227 Pa	6.4944e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	1.0608e-005 m	8.3617e+007 Pa	1.794e-002 m/m
Maximum	1.0608e-004 m	8.3617e+008 Pa	0.1794 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.	0.	1.0608e-005	3.5681e-006
2.		1.5912e-005	5.3521e-006
3.		2.1215e-005	7.1361e-006
4.		2.6519e-005	8.9202e-006
5.		3.1823e-005	1.0704e-005
6.		3.7127e-005	1.2488e-005
7.		4.2431e-005	1.4272e-005
8.		4.7735e-005	1.6056e-005
9.		5.3038e-005	1.784e-005
10.		5.8342e-005	1.9624e-005
11.		6.3646e-005	2.1408e-005
12.		6.895e-005	2.3192e-005
13.		7.4254e-005	2.4976e-005
14.		7.9558e-005	2.6761e-005
15.		8.4862e-005	2.8545e-005
16.		9.0165e-005	3.0329e-005
17.		9.5469e-005	3.2113e-005
18.		1.0077e-004	3.3897e-005

19.		1.0608e-004	3.5681e-005
20.			

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	2.2475e-002	8.3617e+007	5.1865e+006
2.	3.1908e-002	1.2543e+008	7.7797e+006
3.	3.4947e-002	1.6723e+008	1.0373e+007
4.	5.0252e-002	2.0904e+008	1.2966e+007
5.	6.2937e-002	2.5085e+008	1.5559e+007
6.	6.1672e-002	2.9266e+008	1.8153e+007
7.	8.5827e-002	3.3447e+008	2.0746e+007
8.	9.9201e-002	3.7628e+008	2.3339e+007
9.	0.11559	4.1808e+008	2.5932e+007
10.	0.10362	4.5989e+008	2.8526e+007
11.	0.10429	5.017e+008	3.1119e+007
12.	0.1035	5.4351e+008	3.3712e+007
13.	0.15489	5.8532e+008	3.6305e+007
14.	0.12707	6.2713e+008	3.8899e+007
15.	0.17009	6.6894e+008	4.1492e+007
16.	0.14427	7.1074e+008	4.4085e+007
17.	0.14569	7.5255e+008	4.6678e+007
18.	0.19928	7.9436e+008	4.9272e+007
19.			
20.	0.21227	8.3617e+008	5.1865e+007

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	6.7623e-013	1.794e-002	8.0156e-004
2.	9.7281e-013	2.691e-002	1.2023e-003
3.	1.3555e-012	3.588e-002	1.6031e-003
4.	1.5851e-012	4.485e-002	2.0039e-003
5.	2.0442e-012	5.382e-002	2.4047e-003
6.	2.1283e-012	6.279e-002	2.8055e-003
7.	2.5966e-012	7.176e-002	3.2062e-003
8.	2.8973e-012	8.073e-002	3.607e-003
9.	3.233e-012	8.97e-002	4.0078e-003
10.	3.6043e-012	9.867e-002	4.4086e-003
11.	3.9704e-012	0.10764	4.8093e-003
12.	3.8978e-012	0.11661	5.2101e-003
13.	4.5349e-012	0.12558	5.6109e-003
14.	4.9633e-012	0.13455	6.0117e-003
15.	5.1411e-012	0.14352	6.4125e-003
16.	5.6495e-012	0.15249	6.8132e-003
17.	5.7457e-012	0.16146	7.214e-003
18.	6.4944e-012	0.17043	7.6148e-003
19.			
20.	6.406e-012	0.1794	8.0156e-003

Material Data

PTFE

TABLE 27
PTFE > Constants
Density | 2150 kg m⁻³

TABLE 28
PTFE > Color

Red	Green	Blue
181	155	130

TABLE 29
PTFE > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
4.1e+008	0.49	6.8333e+009	1.3758e+008	

TABLE 30
PTFE > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.5e+007

TABLE 31
PTFE > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
7.e+006

Stainless Steel

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 40
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

10-07-2020 13:06

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Unit: Pa

Time: 20

10-07-2020 13:06

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Elastic Strain

Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain

Unit: m/m

Time: 20

10-07-2020 13:07

II. FEM Analysis report for Nylon-12 catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Wednesday, June 17, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

Contents

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 - Loads
 - Solution (B6)
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 - Results
- **Material Data**
 - NYLON 12
 - Stainless Steel

Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	Geometry	
State	Fully Defined	
Definition		
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS	
Type	Iges	
Length Unit	Millimeters	
Element Control	Program Controlled	
Display Style	Body Color	
Bounding Box		
Length X	5.2663e-003 m	
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m	
Properties		
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³	
Mass	1.44e-005 kg	
Scale Factor Value	1.	
Statistics		
Bodies	33	
Active Bodies	33	
Nodes	1298778	
Elements	572198	
Mesh Metric	None	
Update Options		
Assign Default Material	No	
Basic Geometry Options		

Solid Bodies	Yes
Surface Bodies	Yes
Line Bodies	No
Parameters	Independent
Parameter Key	ANS;DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext</i> 12	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [2]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [3]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [4]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [5]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [6]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [7]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [8]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [9]	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i> [10]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	NYLON 12	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	1.3276e-005 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	3.2187e-011 kg·m ²	3.364e-015 kg·m ²	1.0846e-014 kg·m ²	8.036e-015 kg·m ²	1.383e-013 kg·m ²	3.9734e-014 kg·m ²	9.1268e-018 kg·m ²	3.9899e-015 kg·m ²	2.1764e-014 kg·m ²	6.852e-014 kg·m ²	4.5184e-016 kg·m ²

Moment of Inertia Ip2	3.2247e-011 kg-m ²	3.2839e-015 kg-m ²	1.0427e-014 kg-m ²	6.0994e-014 kg-m ²	1.2615e-013 kg-m ²	4.3132e-014 kg-m ²	4.3506e-016 kg-m ²	4.3183e-014 kg-m ²	1.2351e-013 kg-m ²	6.2174e-014 kg-m ²	1.0892e-014 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.976e-012 kg-m ²	8.5963e-017 kg-m ²	4.5001e-016 kg-m ²	6.723e-014 kg-m ²	2.2259e-014 kg-m ²	3.9837e-015 kg-m ²	4.424e-016 kg-m ²	3.978e-014 kg-m ²	1.3538e-013 kg-m ²	8.1706e-015 kg-m ²	1.0471e-014 kg-m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [11]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [12]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [13]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [14]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [15]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [16]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [17]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [18]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [19]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [20]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [21]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m ³	6.8831e-012 m ³	7.003e-012 m ³	2.0829e-012 m ³	4.0944e-012 m ³	1.036e-012 m ³	4.0971e-012 m ³	7.8003e-012 m ³	4.9869e-012 m ³	2.0831e-012 m ³	3.1329e-012 m ³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg-m ²	1.4058e-014 kg-m ²	1.4313e-014 kg-m ²	8.6022e-017 kg-m ²	2.3766e-014 kg-m ²	9.1109e-018 kg-m ²	2.374e-014 kg-m ²	2.1578e-014 kg-m ²	3.9248e-015 kg-m ²	8.6031e-017 kg-m ²	4.5116e-016 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg-m ²	8.8508e-014 kg-m ²	9.0265e-014 kg-m ²	3.2869e-015 kg-m ²	1.5526e-015 kg-m ²	4.3474e-016 kg-m ²	1.5509e-015 kg-m ²	1.2304e-013 kg-m ²	4.2541e-014 kg-m ²	3.2872e-015 kg-m ²	1.0872e-014 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg-m ²	9.799e-014 kg-m ²	9.9888e-014 kg-m ²	3.3668e-015 kg-m ²	2.2364e-014 kg-m ²	4.4206e-016 kg-m ²	2.2339e-014 kg-m ²	1.3482e-013 kg-m ²	3.9182e-014 kg-m ²	3.3671e-015 kg-m ²	1.0452e-014 kg-m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

	<i>WFH</i>										
--	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------	------------

Object Name	<i>mesh folded00</i> [22]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [23]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [24]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [25]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [26]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [27]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [28]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [29]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [30]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [31]	<i>mesh folded00</i> [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-003 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-014 kg·m ²	1.367e-013 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-016 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-014 kg·m ²	1.2475e-013 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-014 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	<i>Materials</i>
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	7
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	<i>Global Coordinate System</i>
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Type	Cartesian

Coordinate System ID	0.
Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces		
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										

Scope Mode	Automatic
Behavior	Program Controlled
Trim Contact	Program Controlled
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m
Suppressed	No
Advanced	
Formulation	Program Controlled
Small Sliding	Program Controlled
Detection Method	Program Controlled
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update											

Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces			5 Faces		4 Faces		1 Face
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										WFH mesh folded00
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping	Geometry Selection										

Method											
Contact	1 Face										
Target	1 Face										
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			
Detection Method	Program Controlled			
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled			

Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	Mesh
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m
Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m
Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	Static Structural (B5)
State	Solved
Definition	
Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural

Solver Target	Mechanical APDL
Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	<i>Analysis Settings</i>
State	Fully Defined
Step Controls	
Number Of Steps	20.
Current Step Number	1.
Step End Time	1. s
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled
Solver Controls	
Solver Type	Program Controlled
Weak Springs	Off
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled
Large Deflection	Off
Inertia Relief	Off
Rotordynamics Controls	
Coriolis Effect	Off
Restart Controls	
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled
Retain Files After Full Solve	No
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled
Nonlinear Controls	
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled
Force Convergence	Program Controlled
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled
Line Search	Program Controlled
Stabilization	Program Controlled
Output Controls	
Stress	Yes
Surface Stress	No
Back Stress	No
Strain	Yes
Contact Data	Yes
Nonlinear Data	No
Nodal Forces	No
Contact Miscellaneous	No
General Miscellaneous	No
Store Results At	All Time Points
Result File Compression	Program Controlled
Analysis Data Management	
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0 \SYS\MECH\
Future Analysis	None
Scratch Solver Files Directory	
Save MAPDL db	No
Contact Summary	Program Controlled
Delete Unneeded Files	Yes
Nonlinear Solution	No
Solver Units	Active System
Solver Unit System	mks

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s
4	4. s
5	5. s

6	6. s
7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	Fixed Support	Force
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By	Vector	
Magnitude	Tabular Data	
Direction	Defined	
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable		Time

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.
4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.

6	6.	3.5
7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	<i>Solution (B6)</i>
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	1 h 40 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.71 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.381 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		
Identifier			
Suppressed	No		

Results			
Minimum	0. m	8.7572e-002 Pa	2.854e-012 m/m
Maximum	1.0644e-005 m	1.7658e+008 Pa	1.7885e-002 m/m
Average	3.75e-006 m	1.5248e+007 Pa	8.1539e-004 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[11]	WFH mesh folded00[19]
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[5]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	3.5933e-003 Pa	2.766e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	8.7572e-002 Pa	2.854e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	1.0644e-006 m	1.7658e+007 Pa	1.7885e-003 m/m
Maximum	1.0644e-005 m	1.7658e+008 Pa	1.7885e-002 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.		1.0644e-006	3.75e-007
2.		1.5966e-006	5.625e-007
3.		2.1289e-006	7.4999e-007
4.		2.6611e-006	9.3749e-007
5.		3.1933e-006	1.125e-006
6.		3.7255e-006	1.3125e-006
7.		4.2577e-006	1.5e-006
8.		4.7899e-006	1.6875e-006
9.	0.	5.3221e-006	1.875e-006
10.		5.8543e-006	2.0625e-006
11.		6.3866e-006	2.25e-006
12.		6.9188e-006	2.4375e-006
13.		7.451e-006	2.625e-006
14.		7.9832e-006	2.8125e-006
15.		8.5154e-006	3e-006
16.		9.0476e-006	3.1875e-006
17.		9.5798e-006	3.375e-006

18.		1.0112e-005	3.5625e-006
19.		1.0644e-005	3.75e-006
20.			

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	3.5933e-003	1.7658e+007	1.5248e+006
2.	6.1244e-003	2.6487e+007	2.2872e+006
3.	1.7073e-002	3.5316e+007	3.0495e+006
4.	2.1903e-002	4.4145e+007	3.8119e+006
5.	1.9813e-002	5.2973e+007	4.5743e+006
6.	3.0709e-002	6.1802e+007	5.3367e+006
7.	1.6337e-002	7.0631e+007	6.0991e+006
8.	3.5459e-002	7.946e+007	6.8615e+006
9.	3.9816e-002	8.8289e+007	7.6238e+006
10.	2.0297e-002	9.7118e+007	8.3862e+006
11.	2.546e-002	1.0595e+008	9.1486e+006
12.	2.5025e-002	1.1478e+008	9.911e+006
13.	5.0943e-002	1.236e+008	1.0673e+007
14.	4.5384e-002	1.3243e+008	1.1436e+007
15.	3.0749e-002	1.4126e+008	1.2198e+007
16.	6.5881e-002	1.5009e+008	1.2961e+007
17.	5.2164e-002	1.5892e+008	1.3723e+007
18.	5.2831e-002	1.6775e+008	1.4485e+007
19.			
20.	8.7572e-002	1.7658e+008	1.5248e+007

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	2.766e-013	1.7885e-003	8.1539e-005
2.	4.1663e-013	2.6827e-003	1.2231e-004
3.	5.7407e-013	3.5769e-003	1.6308e-004
4.	7.1931e-013	4.4712e-003	2.0385e-004
5.	8.016e-013	5.3654e-003	2.4462e-004
6.	9.8308e-013	6.2596e-003	2.8539e-004
7.	1.1121e-012	7.1539e-003	3.2616e-004
8.	1.2495e-012	8.0481e-003	3.6693e-004
9.	1.3613e-012	8.9423e-003	4.077e-004
10.	1.5188e-012	9.8366e-003	4.4846e-004
11.	1.6579e-012	1.0731e-002	4.8923e-004
12.	1.8021e-012	1.1625e-002	5.3e-004
13.	1.8646e-012	1.2519e-002	5.7077e-004
14.	2.0583e-012	1.3414e-002	6.1154e-004
15.	2.1779e-012	1.4308e-002	6.5231e-004
16.	2.3573e-012	1.5202e-002	6.9308e-004
17.	2.479e-012	1.6096e-002	7.3385e-004
18.	2.6252e-012	1.699e-002	7.7462e-004
19.	2.854e-012	1.7885e-002	8.1539e-004
20.	2.854e-012	1.7885e-002	8.1539e-004

Material Data

NYLON 12

TABLE 27
NYLON 12 > Constants
 Density | 1350 kg m⁻³

TABLE 28
NYLON 12 > Color
 Red | Green | Blue
 170 | 170 | 170

TABLE 29
NYLON 12 > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
4.37e+009	0.393	6.8069e+009	1.5686e+009	

TABLE 30
NYLON 12 > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
4.3e+007

TABLE 31
NYLON 12 > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
6.76e+007

Stainless Steel

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 40
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

18-Oct-2020 11:27

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Unit: Pa

Time: 20

18-06-2020 11:31

1.7659e8 Max
1.5696e8
1.3724e8
1.1772e8
9.8009e7
7.8479e7
5.8859e7
3.924e7
1.962e7
0.087572 Min

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Elastic Strain

Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain

Unit: m/m

Time: 20

18-06-2020 11:31

III. FEM Analysis report for PET (Dacron) catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Thursday, June 18, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

Contents

- **Units**
- **Model (B4)**
 - Geometry
 - Parts
 - Materials
 - Coordinate Systems
 - Connections
 - Contacts
 - Contact Regions
 - Mesh
 - **Static Structural (B5)**
 - Analysis Settings
 - Loads
 - Solution (B6)
 - Solution Information
 - Results
- **Material Data**
 - Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON)
 - Stainless Steel

Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	<i>Geometry</i>
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS
Type	Iges
Length Unit	Millimeters
Element Control	Program Controlled
Display Style	Body Color
Bounding Box	
Length X	5.2663e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m
Properties	
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³
Mass	1.3712e-005 kg
Scale Factor Value	1.
Statistics	
Bodies	33
Active Bodies	33
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198
Mesh Metric	None
Update Options	
Assign Default Material	No
Basic Geometry Options	
Solid Bodies	Yes
Surface Bodies	Yes
Line Bodies	No
Parameters	Independent

Parameter Key	ANS;DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext 12</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [2]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [3]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [4]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [5]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [6]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [7]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [8]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [9]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [10]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Polyethelene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON)	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	1.2588e-005 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	3.0518e-011 kg·m ²	3.364e-015 kg·m ²	1.0846e-014 kg·m ²	8.036e-015 kg·m ²	1.383e-013 kg·m ²	3.9734e-014 kg·m ²	9.1268e-018 kg·m ²	3.9899e-015 kg·m ²	2.1764e-014 kg·m ²	6.852e-014 kg·m ²	4.5184e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	3.0575e-011 kg·m ²	3.2839e-015 kg·m ²	1.0427e-014 kg·m ²	6.0994e-014 kg·m ²	1.2615e-013 kg·m ²	4.3132e-014 kg·m ²	4.3506e-016 kg·m ²	4.3183e-014 kg·m ²	1.2351e-013 kg·m ²	6.2174e-014 kg·m ²	1.0892e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.5106e-012 kg·m ²	8.5963e-017 kg·m ²	4.5001e-016 kg·m ²	6.723e-014 kg·m ²	2.2259e-014 kg·m ²	3.9837e-015 kg·m ²	4.424e-016 kg·m ²	3.978e-014 kg·m ²	1.3538e-013 kg·m ²	8.1706e-015 kg·m ²	1.0471e-014 kg·m ²

Statistics											
Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m³	6.8831e-012 m³	7.003e-012 m³	2.0829e-012 m³	4.0944e-012 m³	1.036e-012 m³	4.0971e-012 m³	7.8003e-012 m³	4.9869e-012 m³	2.0831e-012 m³	3.1329e-012 m³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg·m²	1.4058e-014 kg·m²	1.4313e-014 kg·m²	8.6022e-017 kg·m²	2.3766e-014 kg·m²	9.1109e-018 kg·m²	2.374e-014 kg·m²	2.1578e-014 kg·m²	3.9248e-015 kg·m²	8.6031e-017 kg·m²	4.5116e-016 kg·m²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg·m²	8.8508e-014 kg·m²	9.0265e-014 kg·m²	3.2869e-015 kg·m²	1.5526e-015 kg·m²	4.3474e-016 kg·m²	1.5509e-015 kg·m²	1.2304e-013 kg·m²	4.2541e-014 kg·m²	3.2872e-015 kg·m²	1.0872e-014 kg·m²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg·m²	9.799e-014 kg·m²	9.9888e-014 kg·m²	3.3668e-015 kg·m²	2.2364e-014 kg·m²	4.4206e-016 kg·m²	2.2339e-014 kg·m²	1.3482e-013 kg·m²	3.9182e-014 kg·m²	3.3671e-015 kg·m²	1.0452e-014 kg·m²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [22]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											

Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-004 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-015 kg·m ²	1.367e-014 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-014 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-015 kg·m ²	1.2475e-014 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-014 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	Materials
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	7
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	Global Coordinate System
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Type	Cartesian
Coordinate System ID	0.
Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces		
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces				3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										

Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces				3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										

Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces			5 Faces			4 Faces		1 Face
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12											
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	
Protected	No											
Definition												
Type	Bonded											
Scope Mode	Automatic											
Behavior	Program Controlled											
Trim Contact	Program Controlled											
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m											
Suppressed	No											
Advanced												
Formulation	Program Controlled											
Small Sliding	Program Controlled											
Detection Method	Program Controlled											
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Pinball Region	Program Controlled											
Geometric Modification												
Contact Geometry Correction	None											
Target Geometry Correction	None											

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	1 Face										
Target	1 Face										
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection	Program Controlled										

Method	
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[19]	WFH mesh folded00[20]	WFH mesh folded00[21]	WFH mesh folded00[22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[26]	WFH mesh folded00[25]	WFH mesh folded00[24]	WFH mesh folded00[23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			
Detection Method	Program Controlled			
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Pinball Region	Program Controlled			
Geometric Modification				
Contact Geometry Correction	None			
Target Geometry Correction	None			

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	Mesh
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m

Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m
Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	Static Structural (B5)
State	Solved
Definition	
Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural
Solver Target	Mechanical APDL
Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	Analysis Settings
State	Fully Defined
Step Controls	
Number Of Steps	20.
Current Step Number	1.
Step End Time	1. s
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled
Solver Controls	
Solver Type	Program Controlled
Weak Springs	Off
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled
Large Deflection	Off
Inertia Relief	Off
Rotordynamics Controls	
Coriolis Effect	Off
Restart Controls	
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled
Retain Files After Full Solve	No
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled
Nonlinear Controls	
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled
Force Convergence	Program Controlled
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled

Line Search	Program Controlled
Stabilization	Program Controlled
Output Controls	
Stress	Yes
Surface Stress	No
Back Stress	No
Strain	Yes
Contact Data	Yes
Nonlinear Data	No
Nodal Forces	No
Contact Miscellaneous	No
General Miscellaneous	No
Store Results At	All Time Points
Result File Compression	Program Controlled
Analysis Data Management	
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0\SYS\MECH\
Future Analysis	None
Scratch Solver Files Directory	
Save MAPDL db	No
Contact Summary	Program Controlled
Delete Unneeded Files	Yes
Nonlinear Solution	No
Solver Units	Active System
Solver Unit System	mks

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s
4	4. s
5	5. s
6	6. s
7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	Fixed Support	Force
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By	Vector	
Magnitude	Tabular Data	
Direction	Defined	
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable	Time	

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.
4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.
6	6.	3.5
7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	<i>Solution (B6)</i>
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	1 h 35 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.6006 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.381 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		
Identifier			
Suppressed	No		
Results			
Minimum	0. m	9.2018e-002 Pa	3.1415e-012 m/m
Maximum	1.452e-005 m	1.9508e+008 Pa	2.6565e-002 m/m
Average	5.4828e-006 m	1.8902e+007 Pa	1.1624e-003 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[17]	WFH mesh folded00[18]
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[5]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	1.1217e-002 Pa	2.8519e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	9.9096e-002 Pa	3.1415e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	1.452e-006 m	1.9508e+007 Pa	2.6565e-003 m/m
Maximum	1.452e-005 m	1.9508e+008 Pa	2.6565e-002 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.		1.452e-006	5.4828e-007
2.		2.1781e-006	8.2242e-007
3.		2.9041e-006	1.0966e-006
4.		3.6301e-006	1.3707e-006
5.		4.3561e-006	1.6448e-006
6.		5.0821e-006	1.919e-006
7.		5.8082e-006	2.1931e-006
8.		6.5342e-006	2.4673e-006
9.		7.2602e-006	2.7414e-006
10.		7.9862e-006	3.0155e-006
11.	0.	8.7123e-006	3.2897e-006
12.		9.4383e-006	3.5638e-006
13.		1.0164e-005	3.838e-006
14.		1.089e-005	4.1121e-006
15.		1.1616e-005	4.3863e-006
16.		1.2342e-005	4.6604e-006
17.		1.3068e-005	4.9345e-006
18.		1.3794e-005	5.2087e-006
19.			
20.		1.452e-005	5.4828e-006

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	1.1217e-02	1.9508e+007	1.8902e+006
2.	1.2661e-002	2.9263e+007	2.8354e+006
3.	2.0927e-002	3.9017e+007	3.7805e+006
4.	2.6703e-002	4.8771e+007	4.7256e+006
5.	3.1542e-002	5.8525e+007	5.6707e+006
6.	3.479e-002	6.828e+007	6.6158e+006
7.	3.9509e-002	7.8034e+007	7.561e+006
8.	5.4681e-002	8.7788e+007	8.5061e+006
9.	4.9218e-002	9.7542e+007	9.4512e+006
10.	5.6386e-002	1.073e+008	1.0396e+007
11.	5.9637e-002	1.1705e+008	1.1341e+007
12.	6.7539e-002	1.2681e+008	1.2287e+007
13.	6.2525e-002	1.3656e+008	1.3232e+007
14.	7.4648e-002	1.4631e+008	1.4177e+007
15.	8.3973e-002	1.5607e+008	1.5122e+007
16.	8.8108e-002	1.6582e+008	1.6067e+007
17.	7.5822e-002	1.7558e+008	1.7012e+007
18.	9.9096e-002	1.8533e+008	1.7957e+007
19.			
20.	9.2018e-002	1.9508e+008	1.8902e+007

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	2.8519e-013	2.6565e-003	1.1624e-004
2.	4.5926e-013	3.9847e-003	1.7436e-004
3.	6.3334e-013	5.313e-003	2.3248e-004
4.	7.8818e-013	6.6412e-003	2.906e-004
5.	9.4869e-013	7.9695e-003	3.4872e-004
6.	1.1313e-012	9.2977e-003	4.0684e-004
7.	1.3012e-012	1.0626e-002	4.6496e-004
8.	1.3252e-012	1.1954e-002	5.2308e-004
9.	1.6252e-012	1.3282e-002	5.812e-004
10.	1.7476e-012	1.4611e-002	6.3931e-004
11.	1.9428e-012	1.5939e-002	6.9743e-004
12.	2.0436e-012	1.7267e-002	7.5555e-004
13.	2.2021e-012	1.8595e-002	8.1367e-004
14.	2.3593e-012	1.9924e-002	8.7179e-004
15.	2.2742e-012	2.1252e-002	9.2991e-004
16.	2.6935e-012	2.258e-002	9.8803e-004
17.	2.6944e-012	2.3908e-002	1.0462e-003
18.	3.0077e-012	2.5237e-002	1.1043e-003
19.			
20.	3.1415e-012	2.6565e-002	1.1624e-003

Material Data

Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON)

TABLE 27
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON) > Constants

Density	1280 kg m ⁻³
---------	-------------------------

TABLE 28
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON) > Color

Red	Green	Blue
181	155	130

TABLE 29
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON) > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
3.12e+009	0.3	2.6e+009	1.2e+009	

TABLE 30
Polyethylene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON) > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa

6.42e+007

TABLE 31
Polyethelene terephthalate (PET) (DACRON) > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
4.52e+007

Stainless Steel

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 40
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

18-06-2020 13:21

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Unit: Pa

Time: 20

18-06-2020 13:22

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Elastic Strain

Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain

Unit: m/m

Time: 20

18-Dec-2020 13:22

IV. FEM Analysis report for TPUR catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Thursday, June 18, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

Contents

- **Units**
- **Model (B4)**
 - Geometry
 - Parts
 - Materials
 - Coordinate Systems
 - Connections
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 - Contact Regions
 - Mesh
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 - Loads
 - Solution (B6)
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 - Results
- **Material Data**
 - Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR)
 - Stainless Steel

Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	<i>Geometry</i>	
State	Fully Defined	
Definition		
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS	
Type	Iges	
Length Unit	Millimeters	
Element Control	Program Controlled	
Display Style	Body Color	
Bounding Box		
Length X	5.2663e-003 m	
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m	
Properties		
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³	
Mass	1.2925e-005 kg	
Scale Factor Value	1.	
Statistics		
Bodies	33	
Active Bodies	33	
Nodes	1298778	
Elements	572198	
Mesh Metric	None	
Update Options		
Assign Default Material	No	
Basic Geometry Options		
Solid Bodies	Yes	
Surface Bodies	Yes	
Line Bodies	No	
Parameters	Independent	

Parameter Key	ANS;DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext 12</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [2]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [3]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [4]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [5]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [6]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [7]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [8]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [9]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [10]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR)	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	1.1801e-005 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	2.8611e-011 kg·m ²	3.364e-015 kg·m ²	1.0846e-014 kg·m ²	8.036e-015 kg·m ²	1.383e-013 kg·m ²	3.9734e-014 kg·m ²	9.1268e-018 kg·m ²	3.9899e-015 kg·m ²	2.1764e-014 kg·m ²	6.852e-014 kg·m ²	4.5184e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	2.8664e-011 kg·m ²	3.2839e-015 kg·m ²	1.0427e-014 kg·m ²	6.0994e-014 kg·m ²	1.2615e-013 kg·m ²	4.3132e-014 kg·m ²	4.3506e-016 kg·m ²	4.3183e-014 kg·m ²	1.2351e-013 kg·m ²	6.2174e-014 kg·m ²	1.0892e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	7.9787e-012 kg·m ²	8.5963e-017 kg·m ²	4.5001e-016 kg·m ²	6.723e-014 kg·m ²	2.2259e-014 kg·m ²	3.9837e-015 kg·m ²	4.424e-016 kg·m ²	3.978e-014 kg·m ²	1.3538e-013 kg·m ²	8.1706e-015 kg·m ²	1.0471e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											

Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m ³	6.8831e-012 m ³	7.003e-012 m ³	2.0829e-012 m ³	4.0944e-012 m ³	1.036e-012 m ³	4.0971e-012 m ³	7.8003e-012 m ³	4.9869e-012 m ³	2.0831e-012 m ³	3.1329e-012 m ³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg·m ²	1.4058e-014 kg·m ²	1.4313e-014 kg·m ²	8.6022e-017 kg·m ²	2.3766e-015 kg·m ²	9.1109e-018 kg·m ²	2.374e-014 kg·m ²	2.1578e-014 kg·m ²	3.9248e-015 kg·m ²	8.6031e-017 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg·m ²	8.8508e-014 kg·m ²	9.0265e-014 kg·m ²	3.2869e-015 kg·m ²	1.5526e-015 kg·m ²	4.3474e-016 kg·m ²	1.5509e-015 kg·m ²	1.2304e-013 kg·m ²	4.2541e-014 kg·m ²	3.2872e-015 kg·m ²	1.0872e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg·m ²	9.799e-014 kg·m ²	9.9888e-014 kg·m ²	3.3668e-015 kg·m ²	2.2364e-014 kg·m ²	4.4206e-016 kg·m ²	2.2339e-014 kg·m ²	1.3482e-013 kg·m ²	3.9182e-014 kg·m ²	3.3671e-015 kg·m ²	1.0452e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [22]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										

Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-004 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-015 kg·m ²	1.367e-013 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-014 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-014 kg·m ²	1.2475e-013 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-014 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	Materials
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	7
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	Global Coordinate System
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Type	Cartesian
Coordinate System ID	0.
Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces		
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal											

Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces				3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces				4 Faces	3 Faces	
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces			5 Faces		4 Faces		1 Face
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face

Contact Bodies	cath ext 12											WFH mesh folded00
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	
Protected	No											
Definition												
Type	Bonded											
Scope Mode	Automatic											
Behavior	Program Controlled											
Trim Contact	Program Controlled											
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m											
Suppressed	No											
Advanced												
Formulation	Program Controlled											
Small Sliding	Program Controlled											
Detection Method	Program Controlled											
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Pinball Region	Program Controlled											
Geometric Modification												
Contact Geometry Correction	None											
Target Geometry Correction	None											

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	1 Face										
Target	1 Face										
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration	Program Controlled										

Tolerance	
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[19]	WFH mesh folded00[20]	WFH mesh folded00[21]	WFH mesh folded00[22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[26]	WFH mesh folded00[25]	WFH mesh folded00[24]	WFH mesh folded00[23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			
Detection Method	Program Controlled			
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Pinball Region	Program Controlled			
Geometric Modification				
Contact Geometry Correction	None			
Target Geometry Correction	None			

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	Mesh
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m
Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m

Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	Static Structural (B5)
State	Solved
Definition	
Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural
Solver Target	Mechanical APDL
Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	Analysis Settings
State	Fully Defined
Step Controls	
Number Of Steps	20.
Current Step Number	1.
Step End Time	1. s
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled
Solver Controls	
Solver Type	Program Controlled
Weak Springs	Off
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled
Large Deflection	Off
Inertia Relief	Off
Rotordynamics Controls	
Coriolis Effect	Off
Restart Controls	
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled
Retain Files After Full Solve	No
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled
Nonlinear Controls	
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled
Force Convergence	Program Controlled
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled
Line Search	Program Controlled
Stabilization	Program Controlled

Output Controls	
Stress	Yes
Surface Stress	No
Back Stress	No
Strain	Yes
Contact Data	Yes
Nonlinear Data	No
Nodal Forces	No
Contact Miscellaneous	No
General Miscellaneous	No
Store Results At	All Time Points
Result File Compression	Program Controlled
Analysis Data Management	
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0\SYS\MECH\
Future Analysis	None
Scratch Solver Files Directory	
Save MAPDL db	No
Contact Summary	Program Controlled
Delete Unneeded Files	Yes
Nonlinear Solution	No
Solver Units	Active System
Solver Unit System	mks

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s
4	4. s
5	5. s
6	6. s
7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	Fixed Support	Force
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By		Vector
Magnitude		Tabular Data
Direction		Defined
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable		Time

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.
4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.
6	6.	3.5
7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	<i>Solution (B6)</i>
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	2 h 1 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.7246 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.3816 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		
Identifier			
Suppressed	No		
Results			
Minimum	0. m	0.11623 Pa	2.3552e-012 m/m
Maximum	5.7015e-005 m	5.1283e+008 Pa	0.10225 m/m
Average	2.0414e-005 m	3.6462e+007 Pa	4.3936e-003 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[11]	WFH mesh folded00[16]
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[10]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	1.522e-002 Pa	2.8467e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	0.11623 Pa	2.6145e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	5.7015e-006 m	5.1283e+007 Pa	1.0225e-002 m/m
Maximum	5.7015e-005 m	5.1283e+008 Pa	0.10225 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.	0.	5.7015e-006	2.0414e-006
2.		8.5522e-006	3.062e-006
3.		1.1403e-005	4.0827e-006
4.		1.4254e-005	5.1034e-006
5.		1.7104e-005	6.1241e-006
6.		1.9955e-005	7.1447e-006
7.		2.2806e-005	8.1654e-006
8.		2.5657e-005	9.1861e-006
9.		2.8507e-005	1.0207e-005
10.		3.1358e-005	1.1227e-005
11.		3.4209e-005	1.2248e-005
12.		3.706e-005	1.3269e-005
13.		3.991e-005	1.4289e-005
14.		4.2761e-005	1.531e-005
15.		4.5612e-005	1.6331e-005
16.		4.8462e-005	1.7352e-005
17.		5.1313e-005	1.8372e-005
18.		5.4164e-005	1.9393e-005
19.		5.7015e-005	2.0414e-005
20.		5.7015e-005	2.0414e-005

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	1.522e-002	5.1283e+007	3.6462e+006
2.	1.7697e-002	7.6925e+007	5.4693e+006
3.	2.2632e-002	1.0257e+008	7.2924e+006
4.	3.2165e-002	1.2821e+008	9.1155e+006
5.	3.4814e-002	1.5385e+008	1.0939e+007
6.	3.9636e-002	1.7949e+008	1.2762e+007
7.	4.9344e-002	2.0513e+008	1.4585e+007
8.	5.2987e-002	2.3077e+008	1.6408e+007
9.	5.926e-002	2.5642e+008	1.8231e+007
10.	6.4417e-002	2.8206e+008	2.0054e+007
11.	8.3738e-002	3.077e+008	2.1877e+007
12.	7.4012e-002	3.3334e+008	2.37e+007
13.	8.8364e-002	3.5898e+008	2.5523e+007
14.	9.7543e-002	3.8462e+008	2.7346e+007
15.	9.3598e-002	4.1027e+008	2.917e+007
16.	9.9195e-002	4.3591e+008	3.0993e+007
17.	0.10523	4.6155e+008	3.2816e+007
18.	0.11164	4.8719e+008	3.4639e+007
19.			
20.	0.11623	5.1283e+008	3.6462e+007

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	2.8467e-13	1.0225e-002	4.3936e-004
2.	3.5324e-13	1.5338e-002	6.5905e-004
3.	4.7052e-13	2.045e-002	8.7873e-004
4.	7.2191e-13	2.5563e-002	1.0984e-003
5.	7.0643e-13	3.0676e-002	1.3181e-003
6.	8.2395e-13	3.5788e-002	1.5378e-003
7.	1.0836e-12	4.0901e-002	1.7575e-003
8.	1.0618e-12	4.6014e-002	1.9771e-003
9.	1.4499e-12	5.1126e-002	2.1968e-003
10.	1.2984e-12	5.6239e-002	2.4165e-003
11.	1.6682e-12	6.1351e-002	2.6362e-003
12.	1.5275e-12	6.6464e-002	2.8559e-003
13.	2.0227e-12	7.1577e-002	3.0756e-003
14.	2.1648e-12	7.6689e-002	3.2952e-003
15.	2.3279e-12	8.1802e-002	3.5149e-003
16.	2.01e-12	8.6915e-002	3.7346e-003
17.	2.6145e-12	9.2027e-002	3.9543e-003
18.	2.3045e-12	9.714e-002	4.174e-003
19.			
20.	2.3552e-12	0.10225	4.3936e-003

Material Data

Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR)

TABLE 27
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR) > Constants

Density	1200 kg m ⁻³
---------	-------------------------

TABLE 28
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR) > Color

Red	Green	Blue
130	181	143

TABLE 29
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR) > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
7.8e+008	0.4	1.3e+009	2.7857e+008	

TABLE 30
Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPUR) > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa

1.37e+007

Stainless Steel

TABLE 31
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

18-08-2020 15:33

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Units: Pa

Time: 20

18-06-2020 15:34

B: Static Structural
Equivalent Elastic Strain
Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain
Unit: m/m

Time: 20
18-06-2020 15:34

V. FEM Analysis report for HDPE catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Thursday, June 18, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

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Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	<i>Geometry</i>
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS
Type	Iges
Length Unit	Millimeters
Element Control	Program Controlled
Display Style	Body Color
Bounding Box	
Length X	5.2663e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m
Properties	
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³
Mass	1.0506e-005 kg
Scale Factor Value	1.
Statistics	
Bodies	33
Active Bodies	33
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198
Mesh Metric	None
Update Options	
Assign Default Material	No
Basic Geometry Options	
Solid Bodies	Yes
Surface Bodies	Yes
Line Bodies	No
Parameters	Independent

Parameter Key	ANS,DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext 12</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [2]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [3]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [4]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [5]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [6]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [7]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [8]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [9]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [10]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	High Density Polyethylene (HDPE)	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	9.3819e-006 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	2.2746e-011 kg·m ²	3.364e-015 kg·m ²	1.0846e-014 kg·m ²	8.036e-015 kg·m ²	1.383e-013 kg·m ²	3.9734e-014 kg·m ²	9.1268e-018 kg·m ²	3.9899e-015 kg·m ²	2.1764e-014 kg·m ²	6.852e-014 kg·m ²	4.5184e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	2.2788e-011 kg·m ²	3.2839e-015 kg·m ²	1.0427e-014 kg·m ²	6.0994e-014 kg·m ²	1.2615e-013 kg·m ²	4.3132e-014 kg·m ²	4.3506e-016 kg·m ²	4.3183e-014 kg·m ²	1.2351e-013 kg·m ²	6.2174e-014 kg·m ²	1.0892e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	6.343e-012 kg·m ²	8.5963e-017 kg·m ²	4.5001e-016 kg·m ²	6.723e-014 kg·m ²	2.2259e-014 kg·m ²	3.9837e-015 kg·m ²	4.424e-016 kg·m ²	3.978e-014 kg·m ²	1.3538e-013 kg·m ²	8.1706e-015 kg·m ²	1.0471e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											

Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m ³	6.8831e-012 m ³	7.003e-012 m ³	2.0829e-012 m ³	4.0944e-012 m ³	1.036e-012 m ³	4.0971e-012 m ³	7.8003e-012 m ³	4.9869e-012 m ³	2.0831e-012 m ³	3.1329e-012 m ³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg·m ²	1.4058e-014 kg·m ²	1.4313e-014 kg·m ²	8.6022e-017 kg·m ²	2.3766e-014 kg·m ²	9.1109e-018 kg·m ²	2.374e-014 kg·m ²	2.1578e-014 kg·m ²	3.9248e-015 kg·m ²	8.6031e-017 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg·m ²	8.8508e-014 kg·m ²	9.0265e-014 kg·m ²	3.2869e-015 kg·m ²	1.5526e-015 kg·m ²	4.3474e-016 kg·m ²	1.5509e-015 kg·m ²	1.2304e-013 kg·m ²	4.2541e-014 kg·m ²	3.2872e-015 kg·m ²	1.0872e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg·m ²	9.799e-014 kg·m ²	9.9888e-014 kg·m ²	3.3668e-015 kg·m ²	2.2364e-014 kg·m ²	4.4206e-016 kg·m ²	2.2339e-014 kg·m ²	1.3482e-013 kg·m ²	3.9182e-014 kg·m ²	3.3671e-015 kg·m ²	1.0452e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [22]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										

Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-004 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-015 kg·m ²	1.367e-013 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-014 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-014 kg·m ²	1.2475e-013 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-014 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	Materials
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	7
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	Global Coordinate System
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Type	Cartesian
Coordinate System ID	0.
Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11	
State	Fully Defined											
Scope												
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection											
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces			
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces								3 Faces
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12											
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	
Protected	No											
Definition												
Type	Bonded											
Scope Mode	Automatic											
Behavior	Program Controlled											
Trim Contact	Program Controlled											
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m											
Suppressed	No											
Advanced												
Formulation	Program Controlled											
Small Sliding	Program Controlled											
Detection Method	Program Controlled											
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Normal												

Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces		5 Faces		4 Faces		1 Face	
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face

Contact Bodies	cath ext 12											WFH mesh folded00
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	
Protected	No											
Definition												
Type	Bonded											
Scope Mode	Automatic											
Behavior	Program Controlled											
Trim Contact	Program Controlled											
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m											
Suppressed	No											
Advanced												
Formulation	Program Controlled											
Small Sliding	Program Controlled											
Detection Method	Program Controlled											
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled											
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled											
Pinball Region	Program Controlled											
Geometric Modification												
Contact Geometry Correction	None											
Target Geometry Correction	None											

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44	
State	Fully Defined											
Scope												
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection											
Contact	1 Face											
Target	1 Face											
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	
Protected	No											
Definition												
Type	Bonded											
Scope Mode	Automatic											
Behavior	Program Controlled											
Trim Contact	Program Controlled											
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m											
Suppressed	No											
Advanced												
Formulation	Program Controlled											
Small Sliding	Program Controlled											
Detection Method	Program Controlled											
Penetration	Program Controlled											

Tolerance	
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[19]	WFH mesh folded00[20]	WFH mesh folded00[21]	WFH mesh folded00[22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00[26]	WFH mesh folded00[25]	WFH mesh folded00[24]	WFH mesh folded00[23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			
Detection Method	Program Controlled			
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled			
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled			
Pinball Region	Program Controlled			
Geometric Modification				
Contact Geometry Correction	None			
Target Geometry Correction	None			

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	Mesh
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m
Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m

Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	Static Structural (B5)
State	Solved
Definition	
Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural
Solver Target	Mechanical APDL
Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	Analysis Settings
State	Fully Defined
Step Controls	
Number Of Steps	20.
Current Step Number	1.
Step End Time	1. s
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled
Solver Controls	
Solver Type	Program Controlled
Weak Springs	Off
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled
Large Deflection	Off
Inertia Relief	Off
Rotordynamics Controls	
Coriolis Effect	Off
Restart Controls	
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled
Retain Files After Full Solve	No
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled
Nonlinear Controls	
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled
Force Convergence	Program Controlled
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled
Line Search	Program Controlled
Stabilization	Program Controlled

Output Controls		
Stress		Yes
Surface Stress		No
Back Stress		No
Strain		Yes
Contact Data		Yes
Nonlinear Data		No
Nodal Forces		No
Contact Miscellaneous		No
General Miscellaneous		No
Store Results At		All Time Points
Result File Compression		Program Controlled
Analysis Data Management		
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0\SYS\MECH\	
Future Analysis		None
Scratch Solver Files Directory		
Save MAPDL db		No
Contact Summary		Program Controlled
Delete Unneeded Files		Yes
Nonlinear Solution		No
Solver Units		Active System
Solver Unit System		mks

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s
4	4. s
5	5. s
6	6. s
7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	<i>Fixed Support</i>	<i>Force</i>
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By	Vector	
Magnitude	Tabular Data	
Direction	Defined	
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable	Time	

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.
4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.
6	6.	3.5
7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	Solution (B6)
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	1 h 34 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.4951 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.3817 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		
Identifier			
Suppressed	No		
Results			
Minimum	0. m	9.4197e-002 Pa	2.9634e-012 m/m
Maximum	4.6131e-005 m	4.1947e+008 Pa	8.0062e-002 m/m
Average	1.5806e-005 m	3.0854e+007 Pa	3.471e-003 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[16]	
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[10]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	6.9173e-003 Pa	3.0765e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	9.4197e-002 Pa	2.9634e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	4.6131e-006 m	4.1947e+007 Pa	8.0062e-003 m/m
Maximum	4.6131e-005 m	4.1947e+008 Pa	8.0062e-002 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.	0.	4.6131e-006	1.5806e-006
2.		6.9196e-006	2.3709e-006
3.		9.2261e-006	3.1611e-006
4.		1.1533e-005	3.9514e-006
5.		1.3839e-005	4.7417e-006
6.		1.6146e-005	5.532e-006
7.		1.8452e-005	6.3223e-006
8.		2.0759e-005	7.1126e-006
9.		2.3065e-005	7.9029e-006
10.		2.5372e-005	8.6931e-006
11.		2.7678e-005	9.4834e-006
12.		2.9985e-005	1.0274e-005
13.		3.2291e-005	1.1064e-005
14.		3.4598e-005	1.1854e-005
15.		3.6905e-005	1.2645e-005
16.		3.9211e-005	1.3435e-005
17.		4.1518e-005	1.4225e-005
18.		4.3824e-005	1.5015e-005
19.		4.6131e-005	1.5806e-005
20.		4.6131e-005	1.5806e-005

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	6.9173e-003	4.1947e+007	3.0854e+006
2.	1.6133e-002	6.2921e+007	4.6281e+006
3.	1.7121e-002	8.3895e+007	6.1708e+006
4.	1.6949e-002	1.0487e+008	7.7135e+006
5.	2.0597e-002	1.2584e+008	9.2562e+006
6.	2.4703e-002	1.4682e+008	1.0799e+007
7.	2.6999e-002	1.6779e+008	1.2342e+007
8.	4.4939e-002	1.8876e+008	1.3884e+007
9.	2.6083e-002	2.0974e+008	1.5427e+007
10.	4.7837e-002	2.3071e+008	1.697e+007
11.	5.8426e-002	2.5168e+008	1.8512e+007
12.	5.1946e-002	2.7266e+008	2.0055e+007
13.	4.9532e-002	2.9363e+008	2.1598e+007
14.	5.0919e-002	3.1461e+008	2.3141e+007
15.	5.3396e-002	3.3558e+008	2.4683e+007
16.	7.243e-002	3.5655e+008	2.6226e+007
17.	6.022e-002	3.7753e+008	2.7769e+007
18.	8.8515e-002	3.985e+008	2.9311e+007
19.	9.4197e-002	4.1947e+008	3.0854e+007
20.			

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	3.0765e-13	8.0062e-003	3.471e-004
2.	3.9513e-13	1.2009e-002	5.2065e-004
3.	6.2089e-13	1.6012e-002	6.942e-004
4.	7.6424e-13	2.0015e-002	8.6775e-004
5.	9.1918e-13	2.4018e-002	1.0413e-003
6.	1.0686e-12	2.8022e-002	1.2149e-003
7.	1.2272e-12	3.2025e-002	1.3884e-003
8.	1.352e-12	3.6028e-002	1.562e-003
9.	1.4623e-12	4.0031e-002	1.7355e-003
10.	1.6627e-12	4.4034e-002	1.9091e-003
11.	1.7954e-12	4.8037e-002	2.0826e-003
12.	1.9746e-12	5.204e-002	2.2562e-003
13.	2.1547e-12	5.6043e-002	2.4297e-003
14.	2.2954e-12	6.0046e-002	2.6033e-003
15.	2.4499e-12	6.4049e-002	2.7768e-003
16.	2.6438e-12	6.8052e-002	2.9504e-003
17.	2.754e-12	7.2055e-002	3.1239e-003
18.	2.8085e-12	7.6058e-002	3.2975e-003
19.			
20.	2.9634e-12	8.0062e-002	3.471e-003

Material Data

High Density Polyethelene (HDPE)

TABLE 27
High Density Polyethelene (HDPE) > Constants

Density	954 kg m ⁻³
---------	------------------------

TABLE 28
High Density Polyethelene (HDPE) > Color

Red	Green	Blue
109	157	209

TABLE 29
High Density Polyethelene (HDPE) > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
9.76e+008	0.45	3.2533e+009	3.3655e+008	

TABLE 30
High Density Polyethelene (HDPE) > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa

2.61e+007

TABLE 31
High Density Polyethylene (HDPE) > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
1.26e+007

Stainless Steel

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 40
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

18-06-2020 12:17

4.6131e-5 Max

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Unit: Pa

Time: 20

18-06-2020 12:17

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Elastic Strain

Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain

Unit: m/m

Time: 20

18-Oct-2020 15:34

VI. FEM Analysis report for PVC catheter

Project*

First Saved	Monday, June 1, 2020
Last Saved	Thursday, June 18, 2020
Product Version	2019 R2
Save Project Before Solution	No
Save Project After Solution	No

Contents

- **Units**
- **Model (B4)**
 - Geometry
 - Parts
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 - Mesh
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 - Loads
 - Solution (B6)
 - Solution Information
 - Results
- **Material Data**
 - Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC)
 - Stainless Steel

Units

TABLE 1

Unit System	Metric (m, kg, N, s, V, A) Degrees rad/s Celsius
Angle	Degrees
Rotational Velocity	rad/s
Temperature	Celsius

Model (B4)

Geometry

TABLE 2
Model (B4) > Geometry

Object Name	<i>Geometry</i>
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Source	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\cath mesh no ring with cavity.IGS
Type	Iges
Length Unit	Millimeters
Element Control	Program Controlled
Display Style	Body Color
Bounding Box	
Length X	5.2663e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m
Length Z	5.2135e-003 m
Properties	
Volume	9.9793e-009 m ³
Mass	1.3908e-005 kg
Scale Factor Value	1.
Statistics	
Bodies	33
Active Bodies	33
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198
Mesh Metric	None
Update Options	
Assign Default Material	No
Basic Geometry Options	

Solid Bodies	Yes
Surface Bodies	Yes
Line Bodies	No
Parameters	Independent
Parameter Key	ANS;DS
Attributes	No
Named Selections	No
Material Properties	No
Advanced Geometry Options	
Use Associativity	Yes
Coordinate Systems	No
Reader Mode Saves Updated File	No
Use Instances	Yes
Smart CAD Update	Yes
Compare Parts On Update	No
Analysis Type	3-D
Mixed Import Resolution	None
Clean Bodies On Import	No
Stitch Surfaces On Import	Program Tolerance
Decompose Disjoint Geometry	Yes
Enclosure and Symmetry Processing	Yes

TABLE 3
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>cath ext</i> 12	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i>	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [2]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [3]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [4]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [5]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [6]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [7]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [8]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [9]	<i>WFH mesh</i> <i>folded00</i> [10]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC)	Stainless Steel									
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	5.1793e-003 m	3.4513e-004 m	8.5864e-004 m	2.9921e-003 m	3.0739e-003 m	1.7862e-003 m	8.2911e-004 m	2.3758e-003 m	3.472e-003 m	1.9426e-003 m	1.6949e-003 m
Length Y	2.3139e-003 m	7.7138e-004 m	1.3028e-003 m	1.6219e-003 m	1.7046e-003 m	1.7601e-003 m	3.1122e-004 m	1.6892e-003 m	1.6112e-003 m	1.902e-003 m	1.3601e-003 m
Length Z	5.1615e-003 m	1.398e-003 m	1.6966e-003 m	1.9515e-003 m	3.4593e-003 m	2.3701e-003 m	1.1226e-004 m	1.7968e-003 m	3.0744e-003 m	3.0218e-003 m	8.5276e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	9.8343e-009 m ³	2.0816e-012 m ³	3.1304e-012 m ³	5.964e-012 m ³	8.0483e-012 m ³	5.0904e-012 m ³	1.0368e-012 m ³	5.0959e-012 m ³	7.888e-012 m ³	6.0282e-012 m ³	3.1379e-012 m ³
Mass	1.2785e-005 kg	1.6133e-008 kg	2.426e-008 kg	4.6221e-008 kg	6.2375e-008 kg	3.9451e-008 kg	8.0352e-009 kg	3.9493e-008 kg	6.1132e-008 kg	4.6719e-008 kg	2.4319e-008 kg
Centroid X	3.8278e-003 m	5.2048e-003 m	3.5368e-003 m	3.8973e-003 m	4.1425e-003 m	3.2741e-003 m	2.5609e-003 m	3.8098e-003 m	4.1427e-003 m	3.5924e-003 m	2.7566e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.6269e-003 m	1.1211e-003 m	1.3633e-003 m	1.7996e-003 m	1.6767e-003 m	1.732e-003 m	9.2356e-004 m	1.7455e-003 m	1.6778e-003 m	1.7882e-003 m	1.3444e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.9655e-003 m	1.9376e-003 m	5.0884e-003 m	4.2432e-003 m	3.6717e-003 m	4.0071e-003 m	4.8935e-003 m	4.5618e-003 m	3.6976e-003 m	3.9224e-003 m	4.2901e-003 m
	3.0995e-	3.364e-	1.0846e-	8.036e-	1.383e-	3.9734e-	9.1268e-	3.9899e-	2.1764e-	6.852e-	4.5184e-

Moment of Inertia Ip1	011 kg-m ²	015 kg-m ²	014 kg-m ²	015 kg-m ²	013 kg-m ²	014 kg-m ²	018 kg-m ²	015 kg-m ²	014 kg-m ²	014 kg-m ²	016 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	3.1053e-011 kg-m ²	3.2839e-015 kg-m ²	1.0427e-014 kg-m ²	6.0994e-014 kg-m ²	1.2615e-013 kg-m ²	4.3132e-014 kg-m ²	4.3506e-016 kg-m ²	4.3183e-014 kg-m ²	1.2351e-013 kg-m ²	6.2174e-014 kg-m ²	1.0892e-014 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.6435e-012 kg-m ²	8.5963e-017 kg-m ²	4.5001e-016 kg-m ²	6.723e-014 kg-m ²	2.2259e-014 kg-m ²	3.9837e-015 kg-m ²	4.424e-016 kg-m ²	3.978e-014 kg-m ²	1.3538e-013 kg-m ²	8.1706e-015 kg-m ²	1.0471e-014 kg-m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	744957	11269	15456	18449	16548	23290	3931	23391	16886	24515	12134
Elements	466012	2184	3302	3528	2696	4431	756	4620	3033	5040	2286
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 4
Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts

Object Name	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [11]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [12]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [13]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [14]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [15]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [16]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [17]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [18]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [19]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [20]</i>	<i>WFH mesh folded00 [21]</i>
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.0215e-004 m	3.38e-003 m	3.3479e-003 m	1.4091e-003 m	1.772e-003 m	8.2907e-004 m	1.767e-003 m	3.5543e-003 m	2.4046e-003 m	1.409e-003 m	1.6958e-003 m
Length Y	2.7151e-004 m	1.6857e-003 m	1.623e-003 m	8.2235e-004 m	1.6795e-003 m	3.1153e-004 m	1.6793e-003 m	1.6738e-003 m	1.74e-003 m	8.2365e-004 m	1.3592e-003 m
Length Z	8.2664e-004 m	2.3835e-003 m	2.3886e-003 m	3.3056e-004 m	1.5825e-003 m	1.1217e-004 m	1.5839e-003 m	3.0622e-003 m	1.7731e-003 m	3.3013e-004 m	8.4695e-004 m
Properties											
Volume	1.0355e-012 m ³	6.8831e-012 m ³	7.003e-012 m ³	2.0829e-012 m ³	4.0944e-012 m ³	1.036e-012 m ³	4.0971e-012 m ³	7.8003e-012 m ³	4.9869e-012 m ³	2.0831e-012 m ³	3.1329e-012 m ³
Mass	8.0251e-009 kg	5.3344e-008 kg	5.4273e-008 kg	1.6143e-008 kg	3.1732e-008 kg	8.029e-009 kg	3.1752e-008 kg	6.0452e-008 kg	3.8649e-008 kg	1.6144e-008 kg	2.428e-008 kg
Centroid X	5.543e-003 m	3.9919e-003 m	4.4975e-003 m	5.8684e-003 m	2.9833e-003 m	5.9257e-003 m	5.5042e-003 m	4.3372e-003 m	4.6793e-003 m	2.6181e-003 m	5.7301e-003 m
Centroid Y	9.3351e-004 m	1.7624e-003 m	1.7631e-003 m	1.1037e-003 m	1.5728e-003 m	9.2347e-004 m	1.5728e-003 m	1.6719e-003 m	1.7451e-003 m	1.104e-003 m	1.3441e-003 m
Centroid Z	1.8757e-003 m	3.9483e-003 m	3.222e-003 m	2.6209e-003 m	4.1157e-003 m	2.2779e-003 m	3.0561e-003 m	3.4794e-003 m	2.6129e-003 m	4.5506e-003 m	2.8816e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	4.4068e-016 kg-m ²	1.4058e-014 kg-m ²	1.4313e-014 kg-m ²	8.6022e-017 kg-m ²	2.3766e-014 kg-m ²	9.1109e-018 kg-m ²	2.374e-014 kg-m ²	2.1578e-014 kg-m ²	3.9248e-015 kg-m ²	8.6031e-017 kg-m ²	4.5116e-016 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	4.3322e-016 kg-m ²	8.8508e-014 kg-m ²	9.0265e-014 kg-m ²	3.2869e-015 kg-m ²	1.5526e-015 kg-m ²	4.3474e-016 kg-m ²	1.5509e-016 kg-m ²	1.2304e-013 kg-m ²	4.2541e-014 kg-m ²	3.2872e-015 kg-m ²	1.0872e-014 kg-m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	9.1745e-018 kg-m ²	9.799e-014 kg-m ²	9.9888e-014 kg-m ²	3.3668e-015 kg-m ²	2.2364e-014 kg-m ²	4.4206e-016 kg-m ²	2.2339e-014 kg-m ²	1.3482e-013 kg-m ²	3.9182e-014 kg-m ²	3.3671e-015 kg-m ²	1.0452e-014 kg-m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	4444	32382	21588	8727	19519	3760	17482	33938	23391	10676	14689
Elements	882	6402	4130	1680	3887	714	3380	6308	4620	2100	2921
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 5

Model (B4) > Geometry > Parts											
Object Name	WFH mesh folded00 [22]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]
State	Meshed										
Graphics Properties											
Visible	Yes										
Transparency	1										
Definition											
Suppressed	No										
Stiffness Behavior	Flexible										
Coordinate System	Default Coordinate System										
Reference Temperature	By Environment										
Treatment	None										
Material											
Assignment	Stainless Steel										
Nonlinear Effects	Yes										
Thermal Strain Effects	Yes										
Bounding Box											
Length X	1.9455e-003 m	3.0047e-003 m	8.5119e-004 m	3.446e-004 m	1.7947e-003 m	3.1055e-003 m	1.5993e-003 m	1.0267e-004 m	1.5932e-003 m	2.3764e-003 m	2.3805e-003 m
Length Y	1.9019e-003 m	1.741e-003 m	1.299e-003 m	7.7103e-004 m	1.8333e-003 m	1.7066e-003 m	1.6544e-003 m	2.712e-004 m	1.6487e-003 m	1.8284e-003 m	1.7047e-003 m
Length Z	3.0253e-003 m	1.9539e-003 m	1.7004e-003 m	1.3973e-003 m	2.3865e-003 m	3.4612e-003 m	1.7807e-003 m	8.2931e-004 m	1.7774e-003 m	3.3896e-003 m	3.3524e-003 m
Properties											
Volume	6.0276e-012 m ³	6.0329e-012 m ³	3.1364e-012 m ³	2.0812e-012 m ³	5.0628e-012 m ³	7.9566e-012 m ³	4.093e-012 m ³	1.0354e-012 m ³	4.0968e-012 m ³	6.9e-012 m ³	6.8449e-012 m ³
Mass	4.6714e-008 kg	4.6755e-008 kg	2.4307e-008 kg	1.6129e-008 kg	3.9236e-008 kg	6.1663e-008 kg	3.172e-008 kg	8.0247e-009 kg	3.175e-008 kg	5.3475e-008 kg	5.3048e-008 kg
Centroid X	4.8936e-003 m	4.599e-003 m	4.9497e-003 m	3.2817e-003 m	5.2133e-003 m	4.3432e-003 m	4.7816e-003 m	2.9434e-003 m	3.7053e-003 m	4.5956e-003 m	3.8866e-003 m
Centroid Y	1.7879e-003 m	1.799e-003 m	1.3636e-003 m	1.1208e-003 m	1.7323e-003 m	1.6763e-003 m	1.5917e-003 m	9.3335e-004 m	1.5914e-003 m	1.7561e-003 m	1.7611e-003 m
Centroid Z	3.2495e-003 m	2.928e-003 m	2.0832e-003 m	5.2339e-003 m	3.1651e-003 m	3.504e-003 m	2.3147e-003 m	5.2958e-003 m	4.8573e-003 m	3.3521e-003 m	3.8217e-003 m
Moment of Inertia Ip1	6.8558e-014 kg·m ²	8.1827e-015 kg·m ²	1.0869e-014 kg·m ²	3.3627e-015 kg·m ²	3.9389e-014 kg·m ²	1.367e-013 kg·m ²	2.3739e-014 kg·m ²	4.4077e-016 kg·m ²	2.3734e-014 kg·m ²	9.8674e-014 kg·m ²	9.7169e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip2	6.2216e-014 kg·m ²	6.2262e-014 kg·m ²	1.0449e-014 kg·m ²	3.2827e-015 kg·m ²	4.2755e-014 kg·m ²	1.2475e-013 kg·m ²	1.5504e-015 kg·m ²	4.333e-016 kg·m ²	1.5507e-015 kg·m ²	8.9107e-014 kg·m ²	8.7826e-014 kg·m ²
Moment of Inertia Ip3	8.1678e-015 kg·m ²	6.8616e-014 kg·m ²	4.5116e-016 kg·m ²	8.5936e-017 kg·m ²	3.948e-015 kg·m ²	2.1971e-014 kg·m ²	2.2338e-014 kg·m ²	9.1773e-018 kg·m ²	2.2334e-014 kg·m ²	1.4173e-014 kg·m ²	1.3905e-014 kg·m ²
Statistics											
Nodes	27042	25778	14689	8134	16015	19250	18161	5042	17482	31322	14441
Elements	5292	4788	2921	1596	2940	3370	3549	966	3380	6132	2352
Mesh Metric	None										

TABLE 6
Model (B4) > Materials

Object Name	Materials
State	Fully Defined
Statistics	
Materials	7
Material Assignments	0

Coordinate Systems

TABLE 7
Model (B4) > Coordinate Systems > Coordinate System

Object Name	Global Coordinate System
State	Fully Defined

Definition	
Type	Cartesian
Coordinate System ID	0.
Origin	
Origin X	0. m
Origin Y	0. m
Origin Z	0. m
Directional Vectors	
X Axis Data	[1. 0. 0.]
Y Axis Data	[0. 1. 0.]
Z Axis Data	[0. 0. 1.]

Connections

TABLE 8
Model (B4) > Connections

Object Name	Connections
State	Fully Defined
Auto Detection	
Generate Automatic Connection On Refresh	Yes
Transparency	
Enabled	Yes

TABLE 9
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts

Object Name	Contacts
State	Fully Defined
Definition	
Connection Type	Contact
Scope	
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection
Geometry	All Bodies
Auto Detection	
Tolerance Type	Slider
Tolerance Slider	0.
Tolerance Value	1.9408e-005 m
Use Range	No
Face/Face	Yes
Face-Face Angle Tolerance	75. °
Face Overlap Tolerance	Off
Cylindrical Faces	Include
Face/Edge	No
Edge/Edge	No
Priority	Include All
Group By	Bodies
Search Across	Bodies
Statistics	
Connections	48
Active Connections	48

TABLE 10
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region	Contact Region 2	Contact Region 3	Contact Region 4	Contact Region 5	Contact Region 6	Contact Region 7	Contact Region 8	Contact Region 9	Contact Region 10	Contact Region 11
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces	5 Faces		
Target	3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	4 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]
Protected	No										

Definition	
Type	Bonded
Scope Mode	Automatic
Behavior	Program Controlled
Trim Contact	Program Controlled
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m
Suppressed	No
Advanced	
Formulation	Program Controlled
Small Sliding	Program Controlled
Detection Method	Program Controlled
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 11
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 12	Contact Region 13	Contact Region 14	Contact Region 15	Contact Region 16	Contact Region 17	Contact Region 18	Contact Region 19	Contact Region 20	Contact Region 21	Contact Region 22
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	5 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces			3 Faces	4 Faces	6 Faces	4 Faces	3 Faces	
Target	4 Faces	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces	3 Faces		
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal											

Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

TABLE 12
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 23	Contact Region 24	Contact Region 25	Contact Region 26	Contact Region 27	Contact Region 28	Contact Region 29	Contact Region 30	Contact Region 31	Contact Region 32	Contact Region 33
State	Fully Defined										
Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	4 Faces	3 Faces	5 Faces	3 Faces		5 Faces			4 Faces		1 Face
Target	3 Faces		4 Faces	3 Faces			4 Faces		3 Faces	4 Faces	1 Face
Contact Bodies	cath ext 12										WFH mesh folded00
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [23]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [14]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 13
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 34	Contact Region 35	Contact Region 36	Contact Region 37	Contact Region 38	Contact Region 39	Contact Region 40	Contact Region 41	Contact Region 42	Contact Region 43	Contact Region 44
State	Fully Defined										

Scope											
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection										
Contact	1 Face										
Target	1 Face										
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [2]	WFH mesh folded00 [3]	WFH mesh folded00 [4]	WFH mesh folded00 [5]	WFH mesh folded00 [6]	WFH mesh folded00 [11]	WFH mesh folded00 [12]	WFH mesh folded00 [13]	WFH mesh folded00 [15]	WFH mesh folded00 [17]	WFH mesh folded00 [18]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [10]	WFH mesh folded00 [9]	WFH mesh folded00 [8]	WFH mesh folded00 [7]	WFH mesh folded00 [29]	WFH mesh folded00 [16]	WFH mesh folded00 [32]	WFH mesh folded00 [31]	WFH mesh folded00 [30]	WFH mesh folded00 [28]	WFH mesh folded00 [27]
Protected	No										
Definition											
Type	Bonded										
Scope Mode	Automatic										
Behavior	Program Controlled										
Trim Contact	Program Controlled										
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m										
Suppressed	No										
Advanced											
Formulation	Program Controlled										
Small Sliding	Program Controlled										
Detection Method	Program Controlled										
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled										
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled										
Pinball Region	Program Controlled										
Geometric Modification											
Contact Geometry Correction	None										
Target Geometry Correction	None										

TABLE 14
Model (B4) > Connections > Contacts > Contact Regions

Object Name	Contact Region 45	Contact Region 46	Contact Region 47	Contact Region 48
State	Fully Defined			
Scope				
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection			
Contact	1 Face			
Target	1 Face			
Contact Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [19]	WFH mesh folded00 [20]	WFH mesh folded00 [21]	WFH mesh folded00 [22]
Target Bodies	WFH mesh folded00 [26]	WFH mesh folded00 [25]	WFH mesh folded00 [24]	WFH mesh folded00 [23]
Protected	No			
Definition				
Type	Bonded			
Scope Mode	Automatic			
Behavior	Program Controlled			
Trim Contact	Program Controlled			
Trim Tolerance	1.9408e-005 m			
Suppressed	No			
Advanced				
Formulation	Program Controlled			
Small Sliding	Program Controlled			

Detection Method	Program Controlled
Penetration Tolerance	Program Controlled
Elastic Slip Tolerance	Program Controlled
Normal Stiffness	Program Controlled
Update Stiffness	Program Controlled
Pinball Region	Program Controlled
Geometric Modification	
Contact Geometry Correction	None
Target Geometry Correction	None

Mesh

TABLE 15
Model (B4) > Mesh

Object Name	Mesh
State	Solved
Display	
Display Style	Use Geometry Setting
Defaults	
Physics Preference	Mechanical
Element Order	Program Controlled
Element Size	2.e-005 m
Sizing	
Use Adaptive Sizing	Yes
Resolution	Default (2)
Mesh Defeaturing	Yes
Defeature Size	Default
Transition	Fast
Span Angle Center	Coarse
Initial Size Seed	Assembly
Bounding Box Diagonal	7.7633e-003 m
Average Surface Area	3.3182e-007 m ²
Minimum Edge Length	4.0877e-006 m
Quality	
Check Mesh Quality	Yes, Errors
Error Limits	Standard Mechanical
Target Quality	Default (0.050000)
Smoothing	Medium
Mesh Metric	None
Inflation	
Use Automatic Inflation	None
Inflation Option	Smooth Transition
Transition Ratio	0.272
Maximum Layers	5
Growth Rate	1.2
Inflation Algorithm	Pre
View Advanced Options	No
Advanced	
Number of CPUs for Parallel Part Meshing	Program Controlled
Straight Sided Elements	No
Rigid Body Behavior	Dimensionally Reduced
Triangle Surface Mesher	Program Controlled
Topology Checking	Yes
Pinch Tolerance	Please Define
Generate Pinch on Refresh	No
Statistics	
Nodes	1298778
Elements	572198

Static Structural (B5)

TABLE 16
Model (B4) > Analysis

Object Name	Static Structural (B5)
State	Solved
Definition	

Physics Type	Structural
Analysis Type	Static Structural
Solver Target	Mechanical APDL
Options	
Environment Temperature	22. °C
Generate Input Only	No

TABLE 17
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings

Object Name	<i>Analysis Settings</i>	
State	Fully Defined	
Step Controls		
Number Of Steps	20.	
Current Step Number	1.	
Step End Time	1. s	
Auto Time Stepping	Program Controlled	
Solver Controls		
Solver Type	Program Controlled	
Weak Springs	Off	
Solver Pivot Checking	Program Controlled	
Large Deflection	Off	
Inertia Relief	Off	
Rotordynamics Controls		
Coriolis Effect	Off	
Restart Controls		
Generate Restart Points	Program Controlled	
Retain Files After Full Solve	No	
Combine Restart Files	Program Controlled	
Nonlinear Controls		
Newton-Raphson Option	Program Controlled	
Force Convergence	Program Controlled	
Moment Convergence	Program Controlled	
Displacement Convergence	Program Controlled	
Rotation Convergence	Program Controlled	
Line Search	Program Controlled	
Stabilization	Program Controlled	
Output Controls		
Stress	Yes	
Surface Stress	No	
Back Stress	No	
Strain	Yes	
Contact Data	Yes	
Nonlinear Data	No	
Nodal Forces	No	
Contact Miscellaneous	No	
General Miscellaneous	No	
Store Results At	All Time Points	
Result File Compression	Program Controlled	
Analysis Data Management		
Solver Files Directory	C:\Users\Jha_Robotics_Server\Desktop\dhruva ansys folder\ansys graphical_files\dp0 \SYS\MECH\	
Future Analysis	None	
Scratch Solver Files Directory		
Save MAPDL db	No	
Contact Summary	Program Controlled	
Delete Unneeded Files	Yes	
Nonlinear Solution	No	
Solver Units	Active System	
Solver Unit System	mks	

TABLE 18
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Analysis Settings
Step-Specific "Step Controls"

Step	Step End Time
1	1. s
2	2. s
3	3. s

4	4. s
5	5. s
6	6. s
7	7. s
8	8. s
9	9. s
10	10. s
11	11. s
12	12. s
13	13. s
14	14. s
15	15. s
16	16. s
17	17. s
18	18. s
19	19. s
20	20. s

TABLE 19
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Loads

Object Name	Fixed Support	Force
State	Fully Defined	
Scope		
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection	
Geometry	1 Face	
Definition		
Type	Fixed Support	Force
Suppressed	No	
Define By		Vector
Magnitude		Tabular Data
Direction		Defined
Tabular Data		
Independent Variable		Time

FIGURE 1
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

TABLE 20
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Force

Steps	Time [s]	Force [N]
1	0.	0.5
	1.	1.
2	2.	1.5
3	3.	2.

4	4.	2.5
5	5.	3.
6	6.	3.5
7	7.	4.
8	8.	4.5
9	9.	5.
10	10.	5.5
11	11.	6.
12	12.	6.5
13	13.	7.
14	14.	7.5
15	15.	8.
16	16.	8.5
17	17.	9.
18	18.	9.5
19	19.	10.
20	20.	= 10.

Solution (B6)

TABLE 21
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution

Object Name	<i>Solution (B6)</i>
State	Solved
Adaptive Mesh Refinement	
Max Refinement Loops	1.
Refinement Depth	2.
Information	
Status	Done
MAPDL Elapsed Time	1 h 23 m
MAPDL Memory Used	7.543 GB
MAPDL Result File Size	5.3813 GB
Post Processing	
Beam Section Results	No
On Demand Stress/Strain	No

TABLE 22
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Solution Information

Object Name	<i>Solution Information</i>
State	Solved
Solution Information	
Solution Output	Solver Output
Newton-Raphson Residuals	0
Identify Element Violations	0
Update Interval	2.5 s
Display Points	All
FE Connection Visibility	
Activate Visibility	Yes
Display	All FE Connectors
Draw Connections Attached To	All Nodes
Line Color	Connection Type
Visible on Results	No
Line Thickness	Single
Display Type	Lines

TABLE 23
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Results

Object Name	<i>Total Deformation</i>	<i>Equivalent Stress</i>	<i>Equivalent Elastic Strain</i>
State	Solved		
Scope			
Scoping Method	Geometry Selection		
Geometry	All Bodies		
Definition			
Type	Total Deformation	Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress	Equivalent Elastic Strain
By	Time		
Display Time	Last		
Calculate Time History	Yes		

Identifier			
Suppressed	No		
Results			
Minimum	0. m	5.2539e-002 Pa	1.1793e-012 m/m
Maximum	2.1195e-005 m	2.3914e+008 Pa	3.649e-002 m/m
Average	7.5321e-006 m	2.1264e+007 Pa	1.6196e-003 m/m
Minimum Occurs On	cath ext 12	WFH mesh folded00[16]	
Maximum Occurs On	WFH mesh folded00[31]	WFH mesh folded00[5]	cath ext 12
Minimum Value Over Time			
Minimum	0. m	4.7064e-003 Pa	1.0864e-013 m/m
Maximum	0. m	5.2805e-002 Pa	1.1793e-012 m/m
Maximum Value Over Time			
Minimum	2.1195e-006 m	2.3914e+007 Pa	3.649e-003 m/m
Maximum	2.1195e-005 m	2.3914e+008 Pa	3.649e-002 m/m
Information			
Time	20. s		
Load Step	20		
Substep	1		
Iteration Number	20		
Integration Point Results			
Display Option	Averaged		
Average Across Bodies	No		

FIGURE 2
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

TABLE 24
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Total Deformation

Time [s]	Minimum [m]	Maximum [m]	Average [m]
1.		2.1195e-006	7.5321e-007
2.		3.1792e-006	1.1298e-006
3.		4.2389e-006	1.5064e-006
4.		5.2987e-006	1.883e-006
5.		6.3584e-006	2.2596e-006
6.		7.4181e-006	2.6363e-006
7.		8.4778e-006	3.0129e-006
8.		9.5376e-006	3.3895e-006
9.	0.	1.0597e-005	3.7661e-006
10.		1.1657e-005	4.1427e-006
11.		1.2717e-005	4.5193e-006
12.		1.3776e-005	4.8959e-006
13.		1.4836e-005	5.2725e-006
14.		1.5896e-005	5.6491e-006
15.		1.6956e-005	6.0257e-006

16.	1.8015e-005	6.4023e-006
17.	1.9075e-005	6.7789e-006
18.	2.0135e-005	7.1555e-006
19.	2.1195e-005	7.5321e-006
20.		

FIGURE 3
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

TABLE 25
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Stress

Time [s]	Minimum [Pa]	Maximum [Pa]	Average [Pa]
1.	4.7064e-003	2.3914e+007	2.1264e+006
2.	7.8232e-003	3.5871e+007	3.1896e+006
3.	9.1971e-003	4.7828e+007	4.2527e+006
4.	1.3073e-002	5.9785e+007	5.3159e+006
5.	1.4351e-002	7.1742e+007	6.3791e+006
6.	1.9654e-002	8.3699e+007	7.4423e+006
7.	2.098e-002	9.5656e+007	8.5055e+006
8.	2.1186e-002	1.0761e+008	9.5687e+006
9.	2.7406e-002	1.1957e+008	1.0632e+007
10.	2.8861e-002	1.3153e+008	1.1695e+007
11.	2.6575e-002	1.4348e+008	1.2758e+007
12.	3.5501e-002	1.5544e+008	1.3821e+007
13.	3.8389e-002	1.674e+008	1.4885e+007
14.	3.912e-002	1.7935e+008	1.5948e+007
15.	4.4354e-002	1.9131e+008	1.7011e+007
16.	4.0557e-002	2.0327e+008	1.8074e+007
17.	4.2689e-002	2.1522e+008	1.9137e+007
18.	5.2805e-002	2.2718e+008	2.02e+007
19.	5.2539e-002	2.3914e+008	2.1264e+007
20.			

FIGURE 4
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

TABLE 26
Model (B4) > Static Structural (B5) > Solution (B6) > Equivalent Elastic Strain

Time [s]	Minimum [m/m]	Maximum [m/m]	Average [m/m]
1.	1.0864e-013	3.649e-003	1.6196e-004
2.	1.7875e-013	5.4735e-003	2.4294e-004
3.	2.1852e-013	7.298e-003	3.2391e-004
4.	2.9577e-013	9.1226e-003	4.0489e-004
5.	3.2871e-013	1.0947e-002	4.8587e-004
6.	4.0782e-013	1.2772e-002	5.6685e-004
7.	4.745e-013	1.4596e-002	6.4783e-004
8.	4.8694e-013	1.6421e-002	7.2881e-004
9.	5.8899e-013	1.8245e-002	8.0979e-004
10.	6.5599e-013	2.007e-002	8.9076e-004
11.	6.882e-013	2.1894e-002	9.7174e-004
12.	7.4445e-013	2.3719e-002	1.0527e-003
13.	7.9994e-013	2.5543e-002	1.1337e-003
14.	9.0085e-013	2.7368e-002	1.2147e-003
15.	9.3432e-013	2.9192e-002	1.2957e-003
16.	9.8413e-013	3.1017e-002	1.3766e-003
17.	9.8659e-013	3.2841e-002	1.4576e-003
18.	1.1118e-012	3.4666e-002	1.5386e-003
19.			
20.	1.1793e-012	3.649e-002	1.6196e-003

Material Data

Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC)

TABLE 27
Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) > Constants

Density	1300 kg m ⁻³
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TABLE 28
Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) > Color

Red	Green	Blue
181	194	156

TABLE 29
Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
2.16e+009	0.39	3.2727e+009	7.7698e+008	

TABLE 30
Poly Vinyl Chloride (PVC) > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
1.4e+007

Stainless Steel

TABLE 31
Stainless Steel > Constants

Density	7750 kg m ⁻³
Coefficient of Thermal Expansion	1.7e-005 C ⁻¹
Specific Heat	480 J kg ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Thermal Conductivity	15.1 W m ⁻¹ C ⁻¹
Resistivity	7.7e-007 ohm m

TABLE 32
Stainless Steel > Color

Red	Green	Blue
176	154	176

TABLE 33
Stainless Steel > Compressive Ultimate Strength

Compressive Ultimate Strength Pa
0

TABLE 34
Stainless Steel > Compressive Yield Strength

Compressive Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 35
Stainless Steel > Tensile Yield Strength

Tensile Yield Strength Pa
2.07e+008

TABLE 36
Stainless Steel > Tensile Ultimate Strength

Tensile Ultimate Strength Pa
5.86e+008

TABLE 37
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Secant Coefficient of Thermal Expansion

Zero-Thermal-Strain Reference Temperature C
22

TABLE 38
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Elasticity

Young's Modulus Pa	Poisson's Ratio	Bulk Modulus Pa	Shear Modulus Pa	Temperature C
1.93e+011	0.31	1.693e+011	7.3664e+010	

TABLE 39
Stainless Steel > Isotropic Relative Permeability

Relative Permeability
1

B: Static Structural

Total Deformation

Type: Total Deformation

Unit: m

Time: 20

19-06-2020 11:56

B: Static Structural

Equivalent Stress

Type: Equivalent (von-Mises) Stress

Unit: Pa

Time: 20

19-06-2020 11:59

B: Static Structural
Equivalent Elastic Strain
Type: Equivalent Elastic Strain
Unit: m/m

Time: 20
19-06-2020 11:59

- 0.03649 Max
- 0.032436
- 0.028881
- 0.024927
- 0.020272
- 0.016218
- 0.012163
- 0.0081089
- 0.0040545
- 1.1793e-12 Min

